

DRIVING IN THE FAST LANE WITHOUT SAFETY BELT?

— Indian Auto Industry and
Preferential Trade Negotiations

Occasional Paper - 01

CDPP

CENTRE FOR
DEVELOPMENT
POLICY AND
PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT*

After launch of the Make in India scheme in 2014, Automobile sector in the country is receiving close attention of the policymakers. On one hand, as the country aspires to emerge as a major exporter of various automobile categories (two, three and four-wheelers, including passenger as well as commercial vehicles) and auto-components, the market is protected by tariff barriers. On the other hand, the sector is integrated with the world through India's Regional Trade Agreement (RTA) deals, in anticipation of increased market access and consequent export opportunities. However, as India's tariff level is at a relatively higher plane vis-à-vis partner countries, the possibility of rising imports in the aftermath of the trade agreement cannot be ruled out. In addition, the absence of harmonization of technical standards can also impede the market access for Indian exports, even in the aftermath of deep tariff reforms. The global auto-sector standard harmonization is done under the wings of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) forums. While India has joined the UNECE 1998 agreement with effect from April 2006, difference in the UNECE forum participation pattern among its current and potential RTA partners might put a dampening effect on India's future exports. The WITS-SMART tariff reform simulation analysis for ten partner countries indicate that India needs to contemplate on the UNECE membership question closely and evaluate its options judiciously to maximize potential benefits.

Keywords: Automobile sector, India, Trade Bloc, UNECE standards, WITS-SMART Tariff Simulation

JEL Classification: F13, F15, F17

**The views expressed are personal*

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INTRODUCTION

After embracing economic liberalization and export-oriented growth model in 1991, India depended on the multilateral route for export promotion for the next one and a half decades. The orientation was considered pragmatic during mid-nineties, as after inception of WTO in 1995, Indian exports witnessed medium growth opportunities (Nag and Chakraborty, 2006). However, the perspective of the country towards WTO-led reforms changed in the post-2005 period for two reasons. First, given the slow pace of WTO negotiations over the first decade of its existence, in the subsequent period the country started gravitating towards participation in regional trade agreements (RTA) for trade promotions (primarily exports) more intensively (Chakraborty et al, 2022). Second, the insufficient representation of Indian viewpoints at the WTO Ministerial Meeting Declarations and limited success at negotiation forums on reform modalities (e.g., tariff reform formula for enhancing the agricultural and non-agricultural market access) led the country to reduce reliance on multilateral reform process (Chaisse and Chakraborty, 2021; Ranjan, 2006). The country signed a number of RTAs in the subsequent period (Pandey and Unnikrishnan, 2023). Considering the potential economic benefits from collaborations with East and Southeast Asia, the country first entered into the Comprehensive Economic Cooperation Agreement (CECA) with Singapore in 2005, followed by the South Asian Free Trade Area (SAFTA) (2006), ASEAN-India Free Trade Agreement (2010), India-Republic of Korea Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (2010), India-Malaysia Comprehensive Economic Cooperation Agreement (2011) and India-Japan Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (2010). The country also joined the negotiations for Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP), which intended to integrate ASEAN and six of its RTA partners in 2013. The orientation towards deepening of trade flows with the ‘east’ became obvious from the replacement of the existing ‘Look East Policy’ (1991) by the ‘Act East Policy’ (2014) (Palit, 2016). It has been observed that while India’s trade relations with the RTA partners countries have gradually intensified, the country has been able to effectively utilise exports efficiency to the RTA partner countries (Kaushal, 2022).

However, in November 2019, India opted out from RCEP negotiations by citing domestic economic considerations, namely, potential import threat arising from the growing import flows (Ray Chaudhuri and Chakraborty, 2021; Gaur, 2022). The decision was welcomed by a segment of the domestic industry, underlining the perceived threat from the mega-bloc negotiations (PTI, 2019). The RCEP deal reached conclusion during November 2020, and India preferred to stay

away on the ground of un-fulfilled trade-related challenges (Roche, 2020). While the move protected the Indian market, the potential losses from not joining a vibrant trade bloc characterized by deep-rooted international production networks (IPNs) can be significant (ADB, 2022). Several empirical estimates however later confirmed that India may not benefit by re-joining RCEP (Pant and Paul, 2018; Sharma et al, 2020).

The future course of Indian RTA drive seems drawn from the subsequent initiatives. First, it becomes apparent that India would prefer joining bilateral agreements, from its signing of the India-UAE Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA) and Australia-India Economic Cooperation and Trade Agreement (ECTA) in May and December 2022 respectively. Moreover, the continued negotiations for the upcoming RTA with New Zealand shows that the engagement with the ‘East’ will be on, but perhaps not in the form of RCEP. Second, the country weighed the idea of entering into free trade agreements (FTAs) with the ‘West’ (i.e., Canada, EU and US) more seriously for export promotion in recent times (Sikarwar, 2020). The economic motivation is understandable, as entering into RTAs with relatively high-cost developed economies might pose lesser import-led challenges for domestic players in the country. The decision seems prudent from the fact that major trade benefits are anticipated for India from future trade agreements with both the EU (Khorana and Perdakis, 2010) and the US (Fukase and Martin, 2016). By demanding major tariff reforms in the future partner countries, India is likely to enhance market access for its exports. However, given the fact that India’s tariff level is at a relatively higher plane vis-à-vis partner countries, the possibility of rising imports in the aftermath of the trade agreement cannot be ruled out (WTO, 2022). In addition, the existence of difference in standards and procedures often emerges as obstacles to trade, and eventually obstruct trade as potential non-tariff barriers (UNESCAP, 2019). The existence of several standard-related non-tariff barriers (NTBs) on Indian exports in the EU and US markets are well-documented (Verma, 2022). A major challenge for Indian policymakers would be to effectively address these concerns during the RTA negotiations. If the NTB concerns are not addressed while reducing the tariff barriers, a sharp rise in trade volume is unlikely.

While these concerns are true for several product segments, the Indian auto sector exports can be considered as a case in point. In the aftermath of launch of the ‘Make-in-India’ initiative in 2014, the country aspires to emerge as a major exporter of various automobile categories (two, three and four-wheelers, including passenger as well as commercial vehicles) and auto-components.

With the continuous expansion of the domestic market, entry of the major foreign brands is anticipated, and India expects to emerge as a major global auto assembly hub (Exim Bank, 2017). The government has attempted to augment competitiveness of the sector by extending a helpful policy framework (Chakraborty et al, 2019). First, an increase in basic customs duty on several commercial vehicles has been implemented to help the domestic industry to prepare against foreign competition (ET, 2023a). Second, the sector has been prioritized for tariff reforms under various FTA negotiations and accordingly supports have been extended for both the ‘Automobile and Auto Component Industry with budgetary outlay of Rs 25,938 crore over the period of five years’ through Production Linked Incentive (PLI) Scheme (GoI, 2022a). Third, under the Faster Adoption and Manufacturing of Hybrid and Electric Vehicles (FAME) scheme launched in 2015 (which is extended upto 2024 now), consolidation of specialization in EV vehicles and associated machineries (particularly, 2-wheelers, 3-wheelers, buses, charging stations) are being facilitated (GoI, 2022b). Fourth, to augment innovation in the Indian context, the enhanced supports through the National Automotive Testing and R&D Infrastructure Project (NATRiP) enabled the domestic players to augment their capability through association with key facilitation centres, e.g., Mileage Accumulation Chasis Dynamometer (MACD), Engine Test Cell (ETC) and so on (GoI, 2016). All these initiatives are likely to facilitate the long-term goal of India, i.e., ‘to double its auto industry size to Rs. 15 lakh crores by end of year 2024’ (GoI, 2023a).

However, several areas of concern, that might influence future export of auto sector, remain as a potential challenge to fulfil the long-term objective. First, given the homologation requirements in other countries, particularly the future RTA partners, the standard harmonization or the lack of it might play a key role in influencing India’s future export streams. This is all the more important in a period characterized by stringent pollution and emission related norms in line with growing concerns over climate change consequences on one hand and potential embodiment of newer technologies (including artificial intelligence led ones) in the vehicle due to technological advancements on the other (Tripathi et al, 2018). For securing global standard harmonization on road safety involving the automobile sector, the role of different United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) regulations and India’s compliance with the same is very important (Kaizeler, 2020). For instance, India is recently focusing on the EU as a potential RTA partner country. While the EU countries are participating and complying with the UNECE 1958 convention for a long time, India has joined the UNECE 1998 convention only from April 2006

onwards. Given the sharp differences between the coverage and operational features of UNECE 1998 and 1958 standards, export promotion to the partner country, even in the aftermath of the tariff reforms might turn out to be difficult (Chakraborty et al, 2020). Second, if India continues to remain as a member of the UNECE 1998 convention even after the entry into force of the EU-India RTA and consequently the differences in standard persist, the proposition of relocating to India (i.e., to make it a production and export base) may not seem a profitable option for the global auto majors, even in the aftermath of full tariff reforms (i.e., lowering the post-bloc auto tariff to zero percent). In that case, India's dream of turning into a final auto assembly hub, through deepening participation in the GVCs, will remain unfulfilled. Finally, the ongoing discussions on border tax adjustments in EU based on emission patterns is likely to hurt the automobile sector as well (Mishra, 2023).

The current analysis intends to focus on select auto-products, including the segments from both auto-components and vehicles categories, in the context of the proposed Indo-centric FTAs with a few leading partner countries. It has been noted that differences over the expected market access and the actual extent of tariff reforms have been a significant factor in hindering negotiations in some of these ongoing (EAMA, 2023) and potential (Benoit, 2021) FTA partner countries. The paper is arranged along the following lines. The UNECE framework is discussed first, followed by a discussion on India's evolving trade scenario for automobile products. The tariff reform simulation results undertaken in WITS-SMART are reported next, followed by the policy conclusions drawn on their basis.

UNECE FRAMEWORK AND TRADE IMPLICATIONS

The arrangements under United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) WP.29 is the designated global forum for discussions on harmonizing vehicle-related regulations, which are aimed to create a uniform set of standards not only for the assembled final vehicles but also for the auto-components and various parts & equipment that are required during the automotive production value chain. The main objectives of the forum include improving both the active (e.g., relating to lighting and light signalling, brakes, and gears) and passive vehicle safety (e.g., relating to steering, tires, wheel rims, fuel tanks, etc.) norms, while simultaneously securing promotion of environmental sustainability (e.g., setting and periodic revision of pollution standards and emission norms, securing energy efficiency) (UNECE, 2019). Three UNECE WP.29 agreements are in place to date (1958, 1997, and 1998), which are primarily dominated

by the European countries, the Russian Federation, and the United States respectively. The agreements differ significantly in terms of their coverage and operational modalities. For instance, the UNECE 1958 agreement (where standard-setting is generally based on majority voting among the member countries) sets a higher number of standards on finished vehicles and auto-components vis-à-vis the UNECE 1998 agreement (where standard-setting is generally based on consensus mechanism) (Ramos, 2011). It is observed from the relevant documents that the UNECE 1958, 1997, and 1998 forums have 53, 15, and 38 members respectively, which is reflective of their global appeal to countries with sectoral export interests. Interestingly, several developed (e.g., Australia, EU member countries, Japan, South Korea) as well as developing countries (e.g., Malaysia, Nigeria, South Africa, Tunisia) with considerable export interests participate in more than one UNECE forums (e.g., adopting both UNECE 1958 and 1998 norms). It may be noted that Belarus, Kazakhstan, Nigeria, Republic of Moldova and Russian Federation participate in all three UNECE forums.

Membership in multiple UNECE forums is associated with tangible benefits for auto-manufacturing firms located in the participating countries. For instance, when two trading partners happen to be participating countries in the same UNECE agreement, they are more likely to adopt a uniform set of standards, as a result of which it will be easier for any exporting corporate (either a global auto major or any local part and component manufacturing entity) to arrange for automatic approval for their consignment from importing authorities and consequently enhance trade flows. However, if they are from two different UNECE platforms, trade flows might be hindered at the time of cross-border transactions due to the absence of standard harmonization across the component categories in the sectoral value chain. The standard-setting or revision of the existing standards in the UNECE forums is a regular process, depending on the evolving sectoral dynamics. For instance, the recent EU proposal, ‘aim to develop harmonised requirements to remove technical barriers to trade in motor vehicles between the UNECE contracting parties. They also aim to ensure that motor vehicles offer a high level of safety and environmental protection’ (UNECE, 2023).

After India liberalized its auto tariff regime from 1991 onwards, the focus of reform slowly shifted towards procedural and investment-related modifications. After the loss at the WTO on import restrictions relating to the automobile sector (USTR, 2001), the entry to foreign auto players in the Indian market was eased. The consequent spillover effect as well as growing scale

of production of the local players enhanced their motivation to target foreign markets more aggressively, but the standard-related hindrances gradually surfaced. In auto segment Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is now allowed upto 100 per cent under the automatic route, easing the relocation decision of the global auto majors further. The various initiatives Automotive Mission Plan 2016-26 (AMP 2026), including ‘End of Life Policy’ for automotive vehicles and components, adoption of BSV norms by 2019 and implementation of BSVI norms by 2023 for passenger vehicle, is geared up to facilitate this goal. The standard-setting bodies in the country is also actively involved in developing standards for the upcoming segments like Electric and Hybrid vehicles as well as their components (IS 15886) for securing standardization (SESEI, 2018).

Gradually getting wiser on the advantages associated with global auto standard setting framework, India joined the UNECE WP.29 forum initially as an observed in 2003. Recognizing the complexity involved with the component-level, design-level, or sub-system-level standard-related modifications required for compliance with the provisions enacted through the UNECE 1958 agreement (CAR, 2016), and anticipating the potential challenges arising from its majority voting principle adopted therein during future modification of standards; India chose to finally join the UNECE 1998 agreement in April 2006. It can be argued that India’s decision, favouring one UNECE forum (i.e., UNECE 1998 over UNECE 1958 forum) over another, was influenced by the presence of fewer number of Global Technical Regulations (GTR) in the UNECE 1998 agreement and the assurance of embracing the Consensus Principle for future modification of standards therein (Marathe, 2008). The prevalence of Consensus Principle in a forum means that even if one of the participating countries express unwillingness to support the ongoing discussions on adoption of a new set of standard / revision of the existing standards, the entire process can be shelved. The provision was considered crucial in the Indian context, which has a number of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) characterized by capital as well as capacity constraint in the automotive segment (Sudan, 2020). Since joining the UNECE 1998 forum in 2006, India gradually aligned a significant proportion of its domestic safety regulations with the corresponding UNECE norms (GoI, 2018).

The recent focus on EU-India Bilateral Trade and Investment Agreement (BTIA) negotiations, which was in the backburner for a long time due to difference over reform modalities (Chaisse and Chakraborty, 2014; Hildegunn, 2023), brings the focus back on the UNECE 1998 question.

EU has already asked India to join the UNECE 1958 forum for improving road safety on one hand and enhancing trade opportunities on the other (Business Europe, 2021). It is acknowledged in the existing literature that while by joining in the UNECE 1998 forum India's market access to EU partner countries may potentially increase, realized export opportunities for auto-products to most of the UNECE 1958 countries (e.g., EU members) may remain limited even after tariff reforms (Chakraborty and Nag, 2021; Chakraborty *et al.*, 2021; Chakraborty *et al.*, 2022). It can be argued that the modest performance may originate from lower tariff barriers prevailing in partner countries on one hand and due to differences in technical standards on the other, which is integrated in the trade flows data over the period. Perhaps in recognition of this perspective, stressing the need to pursue the developing country markets, rather than focusing explicitly on the developed country segments, ACMA (2017) noted that, ‘.. under the Automotive Mission Plan 2026, India should focus on increasing market penetration in existing markets and develop ties with new emerging markets of Brazil, Iran, South Africa, etc. through bilateral agreements and expansion of existing trade agreements like MERCOSUR PTA that is up for discussion and renewal.’

EVOLVING TRADE SCENARIO AND UPCOMING FUTURE

Given this background, an analysis of India's trade pattern in auto sector related products by the UNECE membership of the partner countries can provide crucial policy insights for future RTA negotiations. For the purpose of the analysis, the partner countries of India have been divided into the following four groups, based on their association with UNECE standards: (A) countries who have joined the 1958 Agreement (dominated by EU members, Thailand, Ukraine), (B) countries who have joined the 1998 Agreement (e.g., US, Canada, India, China), (C) countries who have joined both the 1958 and 1998 Agreements, complying with both set of standards (e.g., EU, Japan, UK, Australia, South Africa), termed in the current context as Common Contracting Parties (CPs), and (D) countries who have decided not to join any of the UNECE agreements (e.g., Latin American nations and African countries except Nigeria, South Africa and Tunisia), clubbed under the expression Rest of the World (ROW).

Figures 1 and 2 underline the proportional importance of different partner groups in India's export and import baskets involving the selected auto-products³ since 2001, so that the evolving dynamics after India's association with UNECE 1998 regime from 2006 onwards can be identified. It is observed from Figure 1 that since 2006, India's exports towards UNECE 1998 members (excluding common CPs) have shown an increasing trend, as anticipated. Interestingly, India's export share towards common CPs (i.e., twelve countries who are participating both in UNECE 1958 and 1998 Agreements) increased till 2009 but declined afterwards. The role of possible hindrances in complying with UNECE 1958 standards in these countries cannot be ruled out. Conversely, the proportional importance of UNECE 1958 countries in India's export basket remained approximately at the same level. Finally, twenty-two countries without having any UNECE affiliation (i.e., ROW) emerged as the most significant export destination. In all, India's enhanced export orientation towards UNECE 1998 (facilitated by common standard) and ROW (helped by no standard compliance requirements) countries is obvious from the analysis.

The analysis in Figure 2 supplement the observations noted in the earlier table. It is observed that the proportional import shares from the UNECE 1998 members are increasing over the period, while the imports from common CPs have shown a declining trend. This indicates a tangible influence of standard harmonization with UNECE 1998 partner countries. Interestingly, India's imports from ROW and UNECE 1958 members have remained around the same level over the study period, indicating modest influence of non-partnership with UNECE 1998 countries, apart from the tariff barriers, on this front so far.

³ Following Chakraborty et al. (2020), the auto-products considered here are drawn from nine different segments, namely: Plastic Products (HS 39), Rubber Products (HS 40), Glass and glassware (HS 70), Articles of Iron and Steel (HS 73), Miscellaneous articles of base metal (HS 83), Machinery and Equipment (HS 84), Electrical Equipment (HS 85), Vehicle and parts and accessories thereof (HS 87) and Sign, Cushion etc. (HS 94).

Figure 1: Share of different UNECE Groups in India's Auto Exports (%)

Source: Author's construction based on ITC (undated)

Figure 2: Share of different UNECE Groups in India's Auto Imports (%)

Source: Author's construction based on ITC (undated)

A few interesting observations emerge from Figures 1 and 2. It is indeed indicative that despite joining the UNECE 1998 Agreement in 2006, the ROW continues to be India's major export destination. The observation perhaps can be explained by the flatter learning curve along which the SME players in the Indian automotive sector is progressing on one hand and cautious attitude adopted by the existing exporters vis-à-vis compliance with the UNECE 1958 standards on the other. It is further noted that India is also enjoying a significant trade relationship with the Common CP countries, which can be viewed in light of the understandable commonality in compliance patterns with UNECE 1998 norms. Conversely, India's existing trade relationship with partners having membership only at the UNECE 1958 forum is relatively low. In case India embraces membership at the UNECE 1958 Agreement in future, trade opportunities with both UNECE 1958 members and Common CPs may further widen. Moreover, in terms of imports a declining trend has been witnessed from Common CPs, with a corresponding increase from the UNECE 1998 member countries⁴. The question is whether this emerging pattern may undergo a change following the country's possible participation at the UNECE 1958 forum in future. In addition, it needs to be checked whether joining an RTA with a UNECE 1998 / 1958 / Common CP or ROW country can lead to differential trade consequences.

Figure 3 shows the evolving patterns of India's exports and import figures (reported in USD Million) in the automobile sector (HS 87) over 2001-20 with partner countries belonging to different UNECE groupings. The period of analysis has been divided into four different phases, namely: Phase I - Pre-UNECE engagement days (2001-05); Phase II - Early UNECE association period (2006-10); Phase III – High RTA Orientation (2011-15) and, Phase IV – operationalization of Make-in-India Programme (2016-20), for deciphering the temporal effects coming through the evolutions in policy orientations. It is obvious that India's trade in the auto-sector has increased consistently over the last two decades. The dominance of the ROW and Common CP countries in the export basket and importance of the Common CP countries in the import basket during all the periods also becomes obvious from the Figure.

It can be argued that the potential additional market access in the UNECE 1958 member countries, by entering into an RTA with them may turn out to be modest, given the relatively

⁴ The trend clearly emerges from the HS 6-digit level trade dynamics, as observed from Trade Map data (ITC, undated).

lower degree of tariff barriers applicable therein (WTO, 2022)⁵. On the other hand, given the relatively higher tariff imposed by India on several auto-products, the prospects of joining any RTA with a country participating at the UNECE 1958 agreement may rather facilitate hassle-free imports and in turn, lead to sectoral trade deficits (Chakraborty et al, 2021).

Figure 3: India’s Trade in Auto Products (HS-87) for different UNECE Groups (Million USD)

Source: Author’s calculation based on ITC (undated)

METHODOLOGY

The Indian perspective on RTA reform in the auto-segment is a function of its past experiences. For instance, the adverse consequences of the past deals have been underlined by noting that RTAs with ‘Japan and South Korea have cost India billions, with South Korean automakers importing “indiscriminately” into India’ (Sachdev, 2023). However, the possible export opportunities through the recent RTAs with Australia and UAE have been anticipated (Soni, 2023). Given the importance of the automobile sector in the Make-in-India programme launched in 2014, the current analysis attempts to understand how a potential deep tariff cut (i.e., reduction

⁵ The average tariff on auto-products and transport equipment in India during 2022 was 31.1 percent vis-à-vis the corresponding figures of 18.8 percent, 9.6 percent, 4.7 percent and 2.6 percent for Brazil, China, the EU and the US respectively (WTO, 2022). A similar conclusion can be drawn from the World Tariff Profiles for the past years as well.

of tariff to zero percent) through upcoming RTAs would influence India's trade scenario. For this purpose, an analysis at the HS 6-digit level with the help of the WITS-SMART simulation tool has been conducted, for understanding whether an RTA with a particular partner with different UNECE backgrounds should help in achieving India's long-term sectoral objectives. Under the partial equilibrium simulation exercise in WITS-SMART framework, the supply-side dynamics on exports in the aftermath of the RTA relationship is observed through price movements. As a country reduces import tariff on partner country exports in the post-bloc period, while simultaneously keeping the corresponding tariff on all other non-partner countries unchanged, the resulting price signal motivates consumers to demand more of the product (from the RTA partner country), which has turned cheaper now. In order to test the validity of this proposition in the current paper, 88⁶ major HS 6-digit level auto-products are considered for analysing the potential effects of deep tariff reforms (i.e., having the post-RTA tariff rate down to zero percent) on both India's export and import trade flows.⁷

To effectively weigh the differential impact of import tariff reforms on partners with different UNECE forum membership, a balanced set of countries needs to be considered here. Ten trade partners have been selected for the current analysis, namely: Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, the EU, Indonesia, New Zealand, South Africa, Thailand and the US. All the selected countries have a considerable presence of domestic players in the finished automobile or auto-component sector and therefore possess keen business interest in this segment. Some of them have got involved in multiple trade discords over auto-related market access with other partner countries at the WTO Dispute Settlement panel.⁸ It is therefore anticipated that any FTA negotiations⁹ with these partners are bound to be guided by strong sectoral interests, leading to tough tariff negotiations. The auto-tariff related rifts have appeared at times during India-EU FTA negotiations (EAMA, 2023) as well as India-US trade agreement deliberations (Raghavan, 2020). Though New Zealand, South Africa and Thailand have not been involved in prior WTO disputes involving

⁶ As India is not trading each of these products with all partners, the number of products reported for country-wise simulations are varying accordingly.

⁷ The current analysis reports only the change in exports for India (i.e., when considered as exporter) in the partner markets (i.e., importer) and vice versa.

⁸ For instance, DS 450 (China — Certain Measures Affecting the Automobile and Automobile-Parts Industries, Complainant: US), DS 342 (China — Measures Affecting Imports of Automobile Parts, Complainant: Canada), DS 339 (China — Measures Affecting Imports of Automobile Parts, Complainant: EU), DS 126 (Australia — Subsidies Provided to Producers and Exporters of Automotive Leather, Complainant: US), DS 81 (Brazil — Measures Affecting Trade and Investment in the Automotive Sector, Complainant: EU), DS 64 (Indonesia — Certain Measures Affecting the Automobile Industry, Complainant: Japan) deserves mention in this context.

⁹ While India entered into an FTA with Australia in 2022, the WITS-SMART analysis with the country have been conducted with 2021 data.

auto-sector market access, their inclusion in the current analysis can be justified by their potential engagement with Indian auto-sector stakeholders in the upcoming period.

The selected countries have been divided into three categories, namely: (a) the potential RTA partner countries of India with whom trade negotiations are currently going on, (b) potential partners with whom no negotiations are currently in progress and (c) the existing RTA partners. India is now actively engaged in trade negotiations with Canada¹⁰, EU¹¹ and New Zealand¹². The country may get involved in RTA negotiations with China¹³, South Africa¹⁴ and US¹⁵ in coming future, while trade agreements already exist with Australia, Brazil, Indonesia and Thailand. However, while the FTA with Australia has been recently signed, the FTAs with Brazil or ASEAN members do not cover the automobile sector comprehensively (Ribeiro, 2021; ASEAN Briefing, 2021).

The three groups also vary across their UNECE membership status. First, Thailand has been selected as representative of UNECE 1958 Agreement. Second, Canada, China and the US have been drawn from the set of UNECE 1998 member countries. Third, Australia, the EU, South

¹⁰ In the recent period both Canada and India have been able to expand bilateral trade flows, with growing complementarities (Tantri and Aulakh, 2019). The launch of the FTA negotiations in 2010 is an acknowledgement of this emerging trend. It is anticipated that the countries will conclude the negotiations by 2023 (Bhattacharyya and Jayasawal, 2023).

¹¹ While the negotiations for a trade agreement with the EU started long back in 2007, the negotiations eventually slowed down due to differences in perspectives over tariff and other non-tariff barriers in automotive products, wine etc. The negotiations have been re-launched in June 2022, in acknowledgement of the fact that EU emerged as India's third largest trading partner, while India has evolved as the bloc's tenth largest trading partner in terms of goods trade (EU, undated). The negotiations have gained pace in recent period (ET, 2023b). However, in addition to the pure economic benefits, strategic considerations may shape the future of the negotiations (Khorana, 2020).

¹² The trade potentials from the India-New Zealand FTA has been noted in the literature (Bano and Paswan, 2016). While the FTA negotiations with New Zealand got delayed due to Covid-related disruptions, recently the two countries have conducted the 1st Round Table Joint meeting between India and New Zealand in June 2023 at New Delhi (GoI, 2023b). It is expected that the trade negotiations will gain momentum in the coming period.

¹³ While India enthusiastically joined the RCEP negotiations in 2013, in anticipation of trade gains through deepening participation in Asian production networks, the trade deficit related considerations (largely with China) forced the country to opt out from the deal in the last stage (Chaisse et al., 2023). After the Galwan Valley experience in 2020, an early conclusion of any trade deal with China seems unlikely. However, a trade agreement with China might reap certain trade benefits for India as well (Kalirajan, 2022).

¹⁴ India's growing trade and investment engagements with Africa and the associated benefits has been noted in the literature (CII-WTO, 2013). While the 1st round of discussions for India-SACU PTA started long back in Pretoria during October 2007, the progress remained slow for some time. The negotiations however has been revived during July 2020, in recognition of growing trade opportunities (GoI, 2020). It is anticipated that the two sides will be able to conclude the agreement shortly, in line with India's growing interests in Africa and possible deepening of Suez Zone ties with Egypt (GoI, 2023c).

¹⁵ The trade potentials from the India-US FTA has been noted in the literature (Fukase and Martin, 2016). The difference of opinion between India and the US on tariff treatment in goods and the ongoing disputes at WTO had been a major bone of contention, functioning as a major impediment for conclusion of the trade deal. During the recent State visit of the Indian Prime Minister Mr. Modi to the US, the two sides however have agreed to terminate the ongoing WTO cases, which may pave the way for an eventual trade deal (USTR, 2023).

Africa and New Zealand represent the Common CP countries, i.e., signatory to both 1958 and 1998 Agreements. Finally, Brazil and Indonesia are members of neither of the UNECE agreements, and therefore, belong to the ROW category. Interestingly, while Brazil is part of the India-MERCOSUR preferential trade agreement (PTA), tariff preferences here have not been extended to all the auto-products by either India or Brazil. In case of Indonesia, full tariff preference has not been extended to India for all the auto-related tariff products. India is currently intent on expanding the coverage of the existing PTA with MERCOSUR, with auto export promotion as a major underlying motivation, but the expectation is not likely to be fulfilled very soon (Mattoo and Mishra, 2023).

EMPIRICAL RESULTS

The detailed product-wise simulation results for each of the selected countries are summarized sequentially in Tables 1-20. For all the ten countries selected for the current analysis, the odd numbered tables first denote the Indian export scenario to the partner country in the aftermath of the tariff reform simulation, followed by the corresponding results involving Indian imports in the even numbered table. For understanding the scenario better, product-wise market penetration in percentage terms as well as the tariff barriers over the last decade have been added in the table. The presentation of trade volume changes, market penetration patterns and tariff protection orientation scenario provide the reader with a comprehensive insight into the evolving dynamics.

A few interesting observations emerge from the simulation results. First, in the UNECE 1958 case, India's trade deficit with respect to Thailand is going to widen in the post tariff reform period. While the market dynamics in Thailand might have a role to play as well, the potential compliance cost with UNECE 1958 regulations may complicate the scenario for India further. Second, in case of the UNECE 1998 countries, a mixed scenario emerges at the macro level. While in case of Canada, a modest rise in the trade surplus can be noted, with respect to China and the US, the trade balance remains positive, but comes down sharply. While the higher tariff prevailing in India vis-à-vis these two partner countries might be a major underlying factor here, the degree of compliance requirements with domestic standards (particularly China) and potential competitions from Common CP countries (i.e., having the advantage of exporting with common UNECE 1998 certification, and additionally aided by higher standard and quality specifications from compliance with UNECE 1958 forum regulations) in the target markets needs to be borne in mind. Third, in case of the Common CP countries, the trade balance has

improved for Australia, New Zealand and South Africa after tariff reduction. However, in case of EU, the trade balance which was positive in the pre-reform period, turns negative afterwards. In line with the experience of the UNECE 1998 countries, the higher tariff prevailing in India can be considered as an important factor here as well. In addition, the compliance requirement with the EU-centric strict adoption of UNECE 1958 regulations might pose a considerable threat to India’s domestic players, particularly as evident, for the import-competing SMEs. The cautions approach adopted by the country during the EU-India trade negotiations needs to be viewed in this light. Finally, in case of Brazil and Indonesia, the ROW representatives, the trade surplus grows after tariff reforms. The result underlines India’s trade advantages with respect to this group of countries, where the market access is not impeded by any specific technical quality requirements. It is also implied from the HS 6-digit wise simulation results that the country will be better off by seeking deep tariff reforms in the auto-segment under the India-ASEAN FTA and Indo-MERCOSUR PTA respectively. The partner country-wise trade balance related observations at the sectoral level are summarized in the pictorial form in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Trade Balance Scenario with Select Partner Countries (USD Million)

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

After launch of the Make in India initiative in 2014, it was expected that the leading global major corporates in key manufacturing segments will relocate to the country and set up / augment their

production base. While quite a few players indeed invested in India for establishing and upscaling their production units, the quantum remind below the expected level so far. Perhaps one key reason behind the modest performance till date had been the unanticipated arrival of the Covid-19 pandemic, which forced many global corporates to reevaluate their investment decisions. However, in the post-pandemic period, wiser from the supply chain uncertainties, many corporates are expressing willingness to consider India as a major production and export base. The recent decision of Apple’s Taiwanese supplier Foxconn to relocate to India and invest in the country to expand production capacity of iPhones is a welcome development in this context (Singh, 2023). The influx of foreign capital and core managerial practices with entry of global players is likely to develop the capacity of the domestic players in the recipient country through the spillover effect on one hand and facilitate its deeper participation in the Global Value Chains (GVCs) and International Production Networks (IPNs) on the other (Amendolagine et al, 2017). A similar expectation is in place for Indian automobile segment, which is deeply linked in the GVCs and (IPNs), as well (Mitra et al, 2020).

India’s participation in the automotive sector GVCs can be traced from the Domestic Value Added (DVA) content in final exports scenario by using the Trade in Value Added (TiVA) database developed by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). The latest TiVA data from their December 2021 update provides detailed country and source industry wise break-up on the export value-added figures for sixty-six economies, and several regional (e.g., Europe, North America) and cooperation-based (e.g., APEC, OECD) groupings as well as RTAs (e.g., ASEAN, EU) over 1995 to 2018. By matching the country-level input-output tables with some modifications (as the tables may be published by national authorities with different periodicity and varying level of industrial classifications), value-addition data on nearly forty aggregated sectors are computed and provided in the database. The rise in DVA content of sectoral exports may indicate that the domestic parts and component segments of that country (i.e., the upstream segments) are gaining in terms of efficiency and quality parameters, as they are replacing the corresponding imports coming earlier from abroad. On the other hand, falling DVA content might indicate a structural or competitiveness-related challenge for the domestic players, including SMEs, in the long run. The DVA content of India’s automotive sector can be observed from Table 21, where the average contribution of the partner countries in its final export has been noted for five consecutive periods, namely: 1995-00 (early WTO participation phase), 2001-05 (changing orientation towards RTAs phase), 2006-10 (active RTA participation

phase), 2011-14 (RTA-led trade balance concern phase) and 2014-18 (adoption of a cautious approach towards the RTAs after launch of the Make in India scheme phase). It is observed that while India's DVA content declined considerably during the RTA enthusiasm phase, a turnaround has been noticed after the adoption of conscious policy initiatives to revive industrial growth after 2014. The rise in share of South and Southeast Asia (a region having participation in both UNECE 1998 and 1958 forums, as well as several Common CP countries) in India's final exports after launch of the 'East'-centric RTAs is a telling observation. A similar occurrence in case of China and the US (UNECE 1998 member) and the EU (Common CP, but having greater focus on UNECE 1958 compliance), in the aftermath of launching any future RTA arrangement with these partners, cannot be ruled out. On the other hand, understandably the share of South American countries (having no association with UNECE standard harmonization process) in India's final exports has remained modest.

The WITS-SMART tariff simulation results involving India's trade in select auto-products and components with potential RTA partners needs to be viewed in this wider context. While India can continue to engage with the world as a member of UNECE 1998 forum and target the fellow member countries and ROW partners for securing export growth, a number of the EU and Asian countries happen to be either UNECE 1958 members or Common CP countries. If India aspires to deepen integration with the GVCs in Europe or even East Asia, the lack of standard harmonization will continue to hamper the country's automotive exports, and in turn, have ramifications for relocation decision of global auto majors in the country. The problem can be quite complex for Indian auto-component manufacturing SMEs, who intend to join the IPNs of leading automobile producing corporates in RTA partner countries as network suppliers in coming days. Perhaps the anticipated benefits of joining UNECE 1958 forum are acknowledged in policy circles but the uncertainties surrounding potential rise in import volumes and the consequent threats for the domestic entities play a bigger role in influencing the cautious approach adopted so far. However, the challenges for Indian auto-sector players, even in the existing RTA partner markets, might demonstrate an interesting dynamic in days to come, as several ASEAN countries are displaying interest to embrace the UNECE 1958 technical standards (Scoles, 2016). Hence, it appears that India needs to contemplate on the UNECE 1958 membership question closely in coming future, keeping all the emerging perspectives in mind, and evaluate its options judiciously to maximize potential benefits.

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Table 1: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select Indian Automobile Exports in Chinese Market

Sl. No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	China Average Share in Indian Exports (%)		Average Tariff Barrier	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	840790	0.08	0.18	123.49	2.19	0.04	15.17	16.57
2	850220	0.04	0.08	91.33	0.05	0.17	10.00	10.00
3	401140	0.00	0.01	72.67	0.20	0.00	0.00	15.00
4	840820	4.37	6.81	55.67	0.54	0.15	15.89	16.50
5	401310	0.00	0.00	45.03	0.00	0.00	15.00	15.00
6	700721	0.06	0.08	36.98	0.12	0.03	11.00	10.40
7	842123	22.44	29.76	32.63	0.48	0.43	10.00	9.60
8	853910	0.05	0.06	29.83	13.69	0.16	10.00	9.60
9	871410	40.65	52.24	28.51	0.56	0.23	23.33	25.67
10	840733	0.05	0.07	27.26	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
11	830210	0.69	0.87	26.41	0.22	0.59	10.00	9.80
12	851240	0.08	0.10	25.55	0.07	0.07	10.00	10.00
13	870600	0.27	0.33	24.33	0.02	0.01	13.00	6.00
14	871690	9.39	11.63	23.86	0.52	0.68	10.00	10.00
15	830230	3.01	3.72	23.72	1.00	1.53	10.00	9.80
16	853110	3.25	3.96	21.72	0.30	0.23	10.00	10.00
17	853180	3.94	4.79	21.63	15.12	4.60	11.94	11.67
18	851220	23.75	28.54	20.19	1.27	1.08	10.00	10.00
19	870840	345.38	414.38	19.98	1.88	5.25	8.77	8.22
20	870893	39.49	47.28	19.72	3.46	4.72	8.86	8.14
21	400941	1.95	2.33	19.66	0.10	0.57	10.50	10.40
22	940560	0.01	0.01	19.31	1.09	0.11	20.00	18.00
23	870830	70.50	83.62	18.61	2.25	1.26	8.84	8.32
24	851140	23.64	27.99	18.41	0.52	1.13	7.27	7.22

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25	853990	5.39	6.37	18.18	8.35	5.07	8.00	8.00
26	848190	171.98	203.20	18.15	4.92	4.73	6.00	7.60
27	842131	3.95	4.63	17.27	1.87	1.47	10.00	10.00
28	853931	0.07	0.09	17.16	0.86	1.45	8.00	8.00
29	851110	0.05	0.05	17.11	0.21	0.10	10.00	9.60
30	851150	0.88	1.03	16.92	0.14	0.20	6.70	6.66
31	851180	10.77	12.59	16.90	0.18	6.33	8.40	8.32
32	853921	2.25	2.62	16.55	1.37	1.64	9.13	8.80
33	831000	0.63	0.73	16.20	0.05	0.10	18.00	16.20
34	392690	103.16	119.76	16.09	2.68	0.91	10.00	10.00
35	870990	0.03	0.04	16.08	1.16	0.82	8.40	8.32
36	870829	72.13	83.68	16.01	1.32	0.23	10.00	9.20
37	870870	16.32	18.91	15.89	2.83	0.95	8.91	8.40
38	851290	5.96	6.89	15.64	1.23	1.08	8.00	8.00
39	830120	0.37	0.42	15.22	0.18	0.75	10.00	9.80
40	870894	13.70	15.76	15.09	1.97	0.28	8.77	8.44
41	848360	15.32	17.60	14.90	2.90	3.02	7.33	7.60
42	871500	0.00	0.00	14.42	2.20	0.07	0.00	6.00
43	401120	7.70	8.74	13.45	0.04	0.03	8.83	9.30
44	851190	9.88	11.17	13.06	1.29	8.18	4.75	4.75
45	870850	89.26	100.50	12.59	1.93	1.82	9.27	8.70
46	853929	0.43	0.48	12.44	0.28	0.22	8.90	8.20
47	401110	0.95	1.07	12.36	0.02	0.02	10.00	10.00
48	848340	238.66	267.65	12.14	18.29	6.69	7.50	7.70
49	840991	64.79	72.65	12.14	6.77	1.68	4.60	5.14
50	848180	588.83	659.61	12.02	3.26	4.59	6.03	6.67
51	870892	2.55	2.85	11.80	0.10	0.32	10.00	9.20
52	853939	0.62	0.70	11.77	0.52	0.21	7.58	7.15
53	850520	1.84	2.05	11.58	2.37	4.55	8.00	8.00
54	870899	119.24	132.76	11.33	1.86	1.18	13.66	12.13

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55	853922	0.01	0.01	11.13	0.00	0.00	7.75	7.20
56	870810	1.29	1.43	11.12	4.07	3.43	10.00	9.20
57	851130	6.46	7.17	10.99	5.62	5.04	6.70	6.66
58	870891	11.24	12.46	10.79	0.81	2.01	10.00	9.20
59	870880	46.58	51.60	10.79	12.25	3.34	10.00	9.20
60	840734	0.12	0.13	10.57	0.07	0.04	10.00	10.00
61	870895	1.96	2.17	10.27	9.86	0.14	10.00	9.20
Medium Export Growth								
62	851230	20.65	22.58	9.38	2.55	3.27	10.00	10.00
63	840999	155.25	167.13	7.65	2.15	2.21	4.39	4.99
64	842129	35.02	37.38	6.75	3.82	4.71	5.00	4.60
65	840890	1574.53	1680.84	6.75	6.72	20.56	6.11	6.10
Low Export Growth								
66	853120	0.53	0.53	0.00	0.67	4.27	0.00	0.00
67	853190	0.57	0.57	0.00	0.46	1.73	0.00	0.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 2: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select Chinese Exports in Indian Market

Sl. No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	China Average Share in Indian Imports (%)		Average Tariff Barrier	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	870600	5.93	66.32	1017.85	5.89	17.37	10.00	11.00
2	840820	0.08	0.37	353.56	2.63	0.15	7.50	9.00
3	850220	1.66	4.71	183.94	7.20	17.62	8.75	9.00
4	851240	5.19	13.82	166.18	13.13	47.62	10.00	11.00
5	700721	12.51	30.12	140.73	38.24	39.62	10.00	10.00
6	870840	37.41	82.68	121.03	7.66	3.93	10.00	11.00
7	870830	47.28	98.03	107.34	15.30	22.98	10.00	11.00
8	840790	4.28	8.84	106.44	8.82	14.69	7.50	7.50
9	840991	53.58	107.39	100.41	10.52	20.71	7.50	9.00
10	853910	0.05	0.11	94.92	69.34	20.45	10.00	11.00
11	871500	9.79	17.20	75.71	91.32	98.34	10.00	10.00
12	851150	2.16	3.78	75.03	3.63	2.95	7.50	9.00
13	842123	4.08	6.78	66.32	5.24	5.92	7.50	8.00
14	870829	93.79	155.63	65.94	10.93	16.69	10.00	11.00
15	853190	21.26	34.67	63.09	29.89	34.47	10.00	10.00
16	840733	1.25	2.03	63.05	0.14	3.21	7.50	9.38
17	870870	67.58	108.96	61.24	51.01	44.95	10.00	11.00
18	870893	15.54	24.43	57.19	12.95	13.00	10.00	11.00
19	401140	1.76	2.76	56.86	38.54	15.99	10.00	10.00
20	870894	76.88	116.25	51.22	30.60	39.79	7.50	9.00
21	851140	12.11	18.29	51.02	5.01	16.14	7.50	9.00
22	830210	47.78	71.32	49.25	46.03	50.23	10.00	11.00
23	830230	6.82	9.91	45.30	5.59	8.18	10.00	11.00
24	401310	0.34	0.47	38.02	11.21	40.86	10.00	10.00

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

25	392690	267.18	367.43	37.52	29.31	34.34	10.00	11.13
26	851190	12.64	17.03	34.74	19.31	25.69	7.50	9.00
27	853180	16.79	22.46	33.80	28.67	41.66	10.00	10.00
28	870810	3.79	4.96	31.09	25.76	7.96	10.00	11.00
29	871690	19.38	24.75	27.71	64.63	86.10	10.00	10.00
30	840732	0.00	0.00	27.48	90.66	68.87	7.50	9.00
31	870850	35.89	45.52	26.82	17.89	22.05	10.00	11.00
32	851220	38.71	48.99	26.55	7.80	16.78	9.17	10.34
33	851110	1.71	2.16	26.24	10.76	11.79	7.50	9.00
34	840999	63.72	80.25	25.93	9.75	11.57	7.50	8.55
35	840734	52.19	65.53	25.55	12.75	15.61	7.50	9.00
36	851130	5.45	6.83	25.32	18.21	19.25	7.50	9.00
37	870821	1.06	1.32	25.25	6.12	3.23	10.00	11.00
38	840890	25.53	31.58	23.70	16.19	13.36	7.50	9.00
39	851120	2.02	2.50	23.48	5.64	53.58	7.50	9.00
40	870892	2.34	2.88	23.26	4.14	5.27	10.00	11.00
41	851180	4.18	5.15	23.03	9.84	32.18	7.50	9.00
42	870891	3.99	4.89	22.54	18.81	23.24	10.00	11.00
43	940560	2.73	3.30	20.95	46.22	57.14	10.00	12.00
44	853929	8.63	10.43	20.92	37.30	43.81	10.00	10.20
45	401220	0.00	0.00	20.56	4.06	3.75	10.00	10.00
46	870880	18.03	21.72	20.47	32.38	19.44	7.50	9.00
47	401219	0.00	0.00	20.29	86.22	10.00	10.00	10.00
48	853110	10.43	12.47	19.57	20.44	25.03	10.00	10.00
49	830120	10.45	12.43	18.96	25.41	30.80	10.00	11.00
50	870990	0.18	0.21	18.35	11.83	10.06	10.00	10.00
51	731100	7.00	8.24	17.77	29.23	27.13	10.00	10.00
52	848180	199.91	234.85	17.48	16.50	14.99	7.50	7.50
53	831000	2.24	2.63	17.22	29.42	23.12	10.00	10.00
54	401120	21.62	25.29	17.01	50.91	69.95	10.00	11.00

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

55	853939	1.79	2.09	16.73	61.97	42.90	10.00	10.00
56	870899	287.57	335.00	16.50	11.65	17.29	10.00	11.00
57	400941	2.43	2.81	15.68	7.84	13.18	10.00	10.00
58	851290	54.19	62.67	15.65	25.02	29.28	7.50	8.00
59	401110	54.18	62.66	15.64	29.17	30.32	10.00	10.50
60	850520	2.13	2.44	14.36	20.44	25.74	7.50	7.50
61	848340	120.93	137.41	13.63	25.19	35.21	7.50	7.50
62	842131	3.24	3.67	13.54	9.62	9.08	7.50	8.00
63	871410	360.09	408.17	13.35	82.86	82.82	10.00	11.00
64	853931	2.63	2.97	13.08	76.41	78.51	10.00	10.00
65	853921	15.38	17.31	12.55	47.59	53.33	10.00	10.33
66	870895	65.75	73.99	12.54	12.40	39.33	10.00	11.00
67	401213	0.58	0.65	12.28	1.47	2.29	3.00	10.00
68	840731	2.68	3.00	11.79	28.48	95.75	7.50	9.38
69	851230	13.21	14.70	11.28	24.33	54.44	8.75	10.00
70	853990	56.37	62.48	10.84	69.04	83.82	10.00	10.00
71	848190	105.95	117.43	10.84	25.14	32.94	7.50	7.50
72	842129	24.18	26.76	10.70	10.18	13.28	7.50	7.50
73	853922	0.14	0.16	10.14	40.99	74.14	10.00	10.00
Medium Export Growth								
74	848360	14.94	16.36	9.52	11.84	14.30	7.50	7.50
Low Export Growth								
75	853120	20.55	20.55	0.00	69.59	58.30	0.00	0.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 3: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select Indian Automobile Exports in US Market

S.No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	USA Average Share in Indian Exports (%)		Average Tariff Barrier	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	840820	12.54	15.12	20.58	12.62	2.10	1.67	1.60
2	850220	34.94	41.63	19.16	27.96	59.68	2.00	2.00
3	700721	0.81	0.91	12.38	17.06	7.27	4.90	4.72
4	392690	53.22	59.40	11.63	27.47	33.46	4.22	4.15
5	940560	0.11	0.13	11.47	32.56	20.65	5.67	5.60
6	871500	0.04	0.05	10.87	1.86	13.27	4.40	4.30
7	870600	42.49	46.77	10.07	6.25	8.98	2.25	2.20
Medium Export Growth								
8	401310	0.43	0.47	9.90	2.59	3.26	3.70	3.56
9	830120	21.59	23.71	9.82	14.52	31.60	5.70	5.56
10	848180	176.78	194.02	9.76	23.29	20.12	3.65	3.62
11	853922	0.08	0.08	8.83	0.05	72.50	4.20	4.06
12	842123	12.43	13.52	8.78	18.07	16.15	2.50	2.40
13	853929	0.39	0.42	8.30	0.32	3.04	3.40	3.32
14	871690	18.92	20.41	7.88	21.92	10.91	2.93	2.88
15	401212	0.55	0.59	7.75	0.27	3.43	3.70	3.66
16	830210	10.27	11.06	7.69	12.97	19.93	2.97	2.91
17	401110	7.08	7.59	7.29	1.87	1.95	3.70	3.66
18	840991	72.96	78.16	7.13	29.02	21.57	2.00	1.92
19	850520	1.14	1.22	7.03	5.24	29.59	3.10	3.08
20	830230	40.98	43.74	6.72	55.90	18.98	2.75	2.70
21	851240	1.87	1.99	6.61	56.13	36.52	2.50	2.40
22	851140	37.83	40.33	6.60	26.20	30.53	2.50	2.40
23	851150	1.37	1.46	6.39	1.00	1.37	2.50	2.40

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

24	848190	266.60	283.46	6.32	32.30	32.46	2.75	2.75
25	870810	2.75	2.91	5.95	34.70	29.93	2.50	2.40
26	851120	0.03	0.03	5.90	16.85	10.09	2.50	2.40
27	401120	51.07	54.08	5.90	1.61	5.15	3.70	3.66
28	853990	1.27	1.35	5.87	18.57	7.12	2.60	2.48
29	853931	0.02	0.02	5.75	0.53	4.14	2.40	2.32
30	853910	0.02	0.03	5.63	1.56	2.03	2.00	2.00
31	851230	5.03	5.31	5.60	16.42	21.23	2.50	2.40
32	842131	6.01	6.35	5.51	25.78	25.46	2.50	2.40
33	401219	0.01	0.02	5.44	2.47	4.32	2.47	2.42
34	848360	15.08	15.89	5.36	12.24	17.50	2.80	2.64
35	870829	28.50	29.96	5.10	23.65	7.25	1.88	1.80
Low Export Growth								
36	851110	0.69	0.72	4.98	0.75	3.21	2.50	2.40
37	851130	0.41	0.43	4.93	1.28	8.33	2.50	2.40
38	851190	13.30	13.95	4.85	20.73	22.63	1.87	1.83
39	400941	13.54	14.16	4.60	28.91	36.74	2.50	2.40
40	848340	301.74	313.84	4.01	20.96	42.65	1.76	1.69
41	851180	0.94	0.98	3.73	5.71	6.49	1.67	1.60
42	870893	23.36	24.18	3.53	17.16	12.92	1.25	1.20
43	851290	3.41	3.53	3.47	15.31	3.67	1.50	1.44
44	870850	251.36	259.71	3.32	23.65	36.68	1.50	1.44
45	853921	0.27	0.28	3.15	5.44	1.53	1.30	1.24
46	870830	242.47	250.09	3.14	25.54	42.89	1.25	1.20
47	853110	12.59	12.97	3.04	1.96	39.19	1.30	1.24
48	851220	5.13	5.28	2.89	7.42	4.79	1.25	1.20
49	840999	212.82	218.84	2.83	33.46	29.13	1.25	1.20
50	840734	0.11	0.12	2.73	0.01	0.11	1.25	1.20
51	870840	135.92	139.52	2.65	11.22	17.96	1.07	1.03
52	870895	0.08	0.08	2.50	0.45	0.55	1.25	1.20

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

53	853939	0.22	0.23	2.19	2.73	15.97	2.40	1.64
54	870870	57.07	58.26	2.10	16.79	44.64	0.83	0.79
55	870894	141.65	144.55	2.05	38.92	32.42	0.83	0.79
56	853180	1.36	1.39	2.05	7.58	17.75	1.30	1.06
57	870891	11.64	11.85	1.83	29.13	22.86	0.83	0.79
58	870880	55.58	56.55	1.74	32.89	46.13	0.94	0.91
59	870892	18.19	18.49	1.63	18.44	31.27	0.83	0.79
60	840733	2.48	2.52	1.61	0.02	2.28	0.63	0.60
61	870899	393.47	399.42	1.51	23.18	22.77	0.77	0.74
62	853190	6.34	6.37	0.49	3.22	19.57	0.65	0.44
63	401140	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.08	1.08	0.00	0.00
64	401220	0.10	0.10	0.00	4.20	2.53	0.00	0.00
65	731100	9.03	9.03	0.00	2.50	6.46	0.00	0.00
66	831000	3.12	3.12	0.00	19.57	22.44	0.00	0.00
67	840732	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.44	0.03	0.00	0.00
68	840790	5.71	5.71	0.00	32.18	21.10	0.00	0.00
69	840890	58.03	58.03	0.00	17.69	12.03	0.00	0.00
70	842129	6.68	6.68	0.00	6.21	2.30	0.00	0.00
71	853120	5.91	5.91	0.00	28.85	19.49	0.00	0.00
72	870990	12.25	12.25	0.00	12.70	4.44	0.00	0.00
73	871410	5.82	5.82	0.00	8.89	3.30	0.00	0.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 4: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select US Automobile Exports in Indian Market

Sl. No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	USA Average Share in Indian Imports (%)		Average Tariff Barrier	
					2014-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	870600	0.51	5.78	10.33	0.06	1.45	10.00	11.25
2	840820	32.48	146.17	3.50	0.45	8.46	7.50	9.00
3	850220	4.94	13.85	1.80	4.47	22.71	8.75	9.00
4	851240	0.38	1.04	1.76	0.80	5.61	10.00	11.00
5	700721	0.60	1.52	1.54	3.64	4.27	10.00	10.00
6	870840	135.32	296.53	1.19	2.57	8.98	10.00	11.00
7	870830	9.79	20.71	1.11	5.06	5.20	10.00	11.00
8	840991	5.13	10.41	1.03	8.56	1.84	7.50	9.00
9	840790	11.21	22.74	1.03	26.35	44.40	7.50	7.50
10	853910	0.08	0.17	1.00	12.47	21.96	10.00	11.00
11	871500	0.00	0.00	0.89	0.59	0.04	10.00	10.00
12	851150	2.45	4.29	0.75	8.57	5.48	7.50	9.00
13	870870	2.97	5.04	0.70	1.59	2.47	10.00	11.00
14	853190	10.00	16.98	0.70	13.57	15.39	10.00	10.00
15	870829	33.24	56.08	0.69	1.74	7.89	10.00	11.00
16	401140	0.01	0.02	0.66	1.08	0.24	10.00	10.00
17	842123	4.49	7.46	0.66	21.38	11.42	7.50	8.00
18	870893	0.86	1.37	0.60	5.84	5.42	10.00	11.00
19	830210	1.86	2.97	0.59	1.65	1.49	10.00	11.00
20	870894	3.16	5.00	0.58	1.67	2.29	7.50	9.00
21	851140	7.96	12.12	0.52	19.13	19.02	7.50	9.00
22	401310	0.00	0.00	0.48	0.66	0.04	10.00	10.00
23	830230	2.22	3.27	0.48	2.51	5.87	10.00	11.00
24	392690	78.69	111.94	0.42	8.86	9.52	10.00	11.13
25	853180	4.78	6.62	0.39	7.03	7.51	10.00	10.00

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

26	871690	1.17	1.61	0.38	3.26	3.03	10.00	10.00
27	851190	3.75	5.15	0.37	3.30	4.99	7.50	9.00
28	940560	0.17	0.23	0.35	5.94	3.87	10.00	12.00
29	870810	3.02	3.97	0.31	4.73	6.08	10.00	11.00
30	851220	4.72	6.17	0.31	2.26	4.63	9.17	10.34
31	871410	1.57	2.04	0.30	0.27	0.76	10.00	11.00
32	851180	1.11	1.43	0.29	18.21	36.62	7.50	9.00
33	870850	20.78	26.71	0.29	5.17	9.01	10.00	11.00
34	851130	0.52	0.67	0.29	5.85	2.32	7.50	9.00
35	731100	1.95	2.50	0.28	7.63	12.14	10.00	10.00
36	851110	2.05	2.61	0.27	23.27	23.06	7.50	9.00
37	840999	66.27	83.41	0.26	14.98	12.67	7.50	8.55
38	853929	0.30	0.38	0.26	2.11	1.04	10.00	10.20
39	870821	0.63	0.80	0.26	2.71	5.12	10.00	11.00
40	401120	0.04	0.05	0.25	1.11	0.21	10.00	11.00
41	840734	66.79	83.45	0.25	0.16	7.79	7.50	9.00
42	870891	1.39	1.74	0.25	2.79	4.46	10.00	11.00
43	851120	1.62	2.01	0.24	6.25	11.61	7.50	9.00
44	830120	0.44	0.55	0.24	2.67	2.28	10.00	11.00
45	870880	4.68	5.79	0.24	2.13	7.66	7.50	9.00
46	870892	2.03	2.51	0.23	1.23	5.16	10.00	11.00
47	401110	1.82	2.24	0.23	1.36	1.61	10.00	10.50
48	853990	0.84	1.02	0.22	3.41	1.50	10.00	10.00
49	853922	0.01	0.01	0.21	1.32	4.70	10.00	10.00
50	401213	0.00	0.00	0.21	2.83	4.46	10.00	8.50
51	853939	0.34	0.41	0.21	4.81	4.59	10.00	10.00
52	853110	5.39	6.51	0.21	11.38	8.71	10.00	10.00
53	851230	0.38	0.45	0.21	3.43	2.91	8.75	10.00
54	853931	0.22	0.26	0.21	1.16	3.52	10.00	10.00
55	853921	1.47	1.77	0.21	2.67	2.60	10.00	10.33

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

56	851290	0.39	0.47	0.20	1.33	0.76	7.50	8.00
57	870899	50.70	60.69	0.20	4.07	4.15	10.00	11.00
58	840890	59.26	70.92	0.20	18.03	21.43	7.50	9.00
59	831000	0.64	0.76	0.20	4.55	9.20	10.00	10.00
60	870895	6.41	7.67	0.20	1.15	3.23	10.00	11.00
61	848180	92.36	110.42	0.20	14.04	31.27	7.50	7.50
62	870990	0.24	0.28	0.18	25.52	11.93	10.00	10.00
63	848340	18.83	21.97	0.17	8.98	6.38	7.50	7.50
64	400941	1.15	1.34	0.17	10.36	8.23	10.00	10.00
65	848190	34.15	39.58	0.16	16.75	13.22	7.50	7.50
66	850520	0.58	0.68	0.16	5.98	5.88	7.50	7.50
67	842131	2.60	2.96	0.14	11.85	11.64	7.50	8.00
68	848360	8.60	9.47	0.10	11.69	10.88	7.50	7.50
69	842129	33.23	36.58	0.10	15.83	19.80	7.50	7.50
Low Export Growth								
70	853120	3.57	3.57	0.00	2.44	6.76	0.00	0.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Occasional Paper – 01
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54	700721	5.64	5.92	5.02	41.27	52.19	2.00	2.00
55	848190	254.10	266.86	5.02	21.98	23.65	2.20	2.20
Low Export Growth								
56	851180	3.81	4.00	4.87	48.31	43.97	1.60	1.92
57	840890	73.80	77.33	4.78	6.33	4.14	2.44	2.56
58	853939	0.21	0.22	4.59	29.06	12.92	2.70	2.40
59	401213	0.01	0.01	4.55	0.59	0.00	2.25	2.25
60	830120	18.73	19.55	4.40	39.73	5.61	2.70	2.70
61	401220	0.17	0.17	4.32	8.51	0.70	2.25	2.25
62	853910	0.79	0.82	4.23	2.14	2.50	1.35	1.35
63	940560	0.20	0.21	4.03	28.21	45.08	2.02	2.02
64	871690	96.31	100.14	3.98	24.99	44.67	1.70	1.70
65	851150	30.73	31.94	3.93	52.38	55.48	1.60	1.60
66	851140	92.79	96.41	3.91	54.78	37.74	1.60	1.60
67	851120	0.60	0.62	3.73	38.61	15.00	1.60	1.60
68	851110	2.32	2.41	3.65	48.40	13.81	1.60	1.60
69	830210	20.77	21.51	3.52	16.89	12.72	1.35	1.35
70	853110	1.52	1.58	3.51	15.87	16.51	1.47	1.47
71	842123	28.30	28.98	2.37	53.04	44.63	0.85	0.85
72	848360	22.83	23.37	2.35	41.49	32.40	1.35	1.35
73	842131	6.01	6.13	1.99	35.76	19.82	0.85	0.85
74	853180	6.84	6.97	1.91	10.48	28.34	0.88	0.69
75	842129	45.46	46.02	1.22	33.57	29.65	0.85	0.68
76	853120	0.94	0.94	0.00	15.76	20.52	0.00	0.00
77	853190	5.50	5.50	0.00	5.50	14.31	1.51	0.33

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Occasional Paper – 01
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61	848180	328.36	382.70	16.55	39.98	29.00	7.50	7.50
62	853921	10.56	12.27	16.21	40.57	35.29	10.00	10.33
63	870892	17.33	19.97	15.26	36.73	33.81	10.00	11.00
64	870899	404.75	465.15	14.92	28.63	28.44	10.00	11.00
65	848340	126.69	143.76	13.47	43.43	35.33	7.50	7.50
66	848190	101.51	115.01	13.30	37.01	33.81	7.50	7.50
67	400941	6.43	7.27	13.03	12.05	27.25	10.00	10.00
68	870990	1.02	1.14	11.50	36.80	66.52	10.00	10.00
69	842131	5.46	6.07	11.14	53.21	42.99	7.50	8.00
Medium Export Growth								
70	850520	7.81	8.52	9.13	55.39	57.08	7.50	7.50
71	842129	53.67	58.20	8.44	44.13	40.32	7.50	7.50
72	401219	0.01	0.01	7.49	0.44	52.86	10.00	10.00
73	848360	51.78	54.59	5.42	50.17	50.50	7.50	7.50
Low Export Growth								
74	853120	2.95	2.95	0.00	8.32	7.06	0.00	0.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

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25	830230	1.66	2.28	37.01	0.00	15.17	16.00	16.00
26	870870	3.66	4.99	36.30	4.31	1.20	16.00	16.00
27	851190	1.98	2.69	36.17	1.19	2.20	16.00	16.00
28	853921	1.49	2.03	35.89	0.91	9.00	18.00	18.00
29	851180	0.01	0.02	35.59	0.32	0.02	17.50	17.50
30	401310	0.09	0.12	35.32	0.81	0.24	16.00	16.00
31	851130	0.01	0.01	34.50	0.02	5.96	18.00	18.00
32	392690	4.60	6.18	34.26	1.40	1.72	12.22	12.22
33	851230	0.23	0.31	34.26	0.20	4.85	18.00	18.00
34	870810	0.77	1.03	34.13	9.54	7.99	18.00	18.00
35	870894	12.16	16.28	33.92	3.70	14.06	16.29	16.29
36	700721	0.44	0.58	32.53	9.04	1.09	12.00	12.00
37	940560	0.00	0.00	32.36	0.13	0.00	0.00	18.00
38	851220	5.94	7.86	32.27	0.36	3.57	18.00	18.00
39	853110	0.04	0.06	32.19	0.06	0.28	18.00	18.00
40	870891	2.89	3.79	31.46	0.34	3.60	18.00	18.00
41	831000	0.00	0.00	30.86	0.01	0.11	16.00	16.00
42	851290	0.12	0.15	30.72	0.33	1.93	16.00	16.00
43	871410	14.36	18.76	30.66	1.76	4.04	16.00	16.00
44	870880	7.33	9.57	30.61	5.31	3.56	18.00	18.00
45	870892	1.99	2.58	29.56	1.92	1.89	18.00	18.00
46	848340	17.79	23.02	29.35	3.74	4.85	14.00	15.20
47	401120	27.43	35.44	29.18	4.35	4.52	16.00	16.00
48	848190	1.54	1.98	28.92	0.65	0.34	15.00	15.00
49	842131	1.88	2.42	28.73	5.97	1.19	16.00	16.00
50	401110	6.89	8.83	28.24	5.27	5.31	16.00	16.00
51	853120	0.00	0.00	28.04	0.07	0.00	12.00	12.00
52	870840	11.02	13.99	26.88	12.51	6.56	11.40	12.50
53	870990	0.00	0.00	26.59	0.68	0.32	14.00	14.00
54	870850	17.66	22.36	26.57	1.24	2.16	13.00	13.00

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55	830120	3.53	4.39	24.38	8.90	7.86	16.00	16.00
56	848360	1.71	2.13	24.07	2.13	2.15	14.00	14.00
57	840999	11.60	14.38	23.94	2.28	1.87	11.29	11.06
58	851110	0.05	0.06	23.04	2.02	0.70	18.00	18.00
59	400941	0.05	0.06	20.83	3.96	2.40	14.00	14.00
60	870895	0.00	0.00	16.42	3.16	0.05	10.00	10.00
61	842129	1.27	1.47	15.77	0.81	0.09	8.40	8.40
62	850520	0.03	0.03	15.36	3.76	0.03	7.00	7.00
63	870899	28.31	32.39	14.41	3.90	5.16	9.00	9.00
64	840890	11.25	12.61	12.07	1.93	3.04	7.00	7.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Occasional Paper – 01
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26	840734	0.00	0.00	27.27	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.25
27	840890	0.06	0.08	26.63	0.03	0.12	7.50	9.00
28	870821	0.00	0.00	26.03	0.01	0.00	10.00	11.25
29	853929	0.00	0.00	25.90	0.06	0.00	10.00	10.20
30	870891	0.44	0.55	25.59	0.07	1.03	10.00	11.00
31	401120	0.04	0.05	25.30	0.17	0.33	10.00	11.00
32	870880	0.22	0.27	24.69	1.61	0.55	7.50	9.00
33	870892	0.23	0.29	24.35	0.96	0.74	10.00	11.00
34	830120	0.02	0.02	24.00	0.68	0.29	10.00	11.00
35	401110	3.02	3.71	22.64	0.08	1.30	10.00	10.50
36	853990	0.00	0.00	22.15	0.03	0.00	10.00	10.00
37	853110	0.03	0.03	22.13	0.01	0.01	10.00	10.00
38	853921	0.00	0.00	21.65	0.09	0.00	10.00	10.33
39	851230	0.00	0.00	21.35	0.68	0.08	8.75	10.00
40	851290	0.02	0.03	20.30	0.65	0.24	7.50	8.00
41	870899	6.87	8.27	20.29	0.36	0.51	10.00	11.00
42	870990	0.00	0.00	19.78	1.77	0.02	10.00	10.00
43	848180	6.05	7.22	19.40	0.81	0.53	7.50	7.50
44	400941	0.01	0.01	17.35	0.03	0.05	10.00	10.00
45	848340	1.58	1.85	17.17	0.30	0.32	7.50	7.50
46	831000	0.00	0.00	16.67	0.07	0.08	10.00	10.00
47	850520	0.01	0.02	16.25	0.04	0.03	7.50	7.50
48	842131	0.02	0.03	15.73	0.74	0.96	7.50	8.00
49	848190	1.72	1.99	15.39	0.71	0.42	7.50	7.50
50	842129	0.21	0.24	12.34	0.12	0.08	7.50	7.50
Medium Export Growth								
51	848360	0.12	0.13	11.11	0.34	0.18	7.50	7.50
Low Export Growth								
52	851110	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	7.50	9.38

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 9: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select Indian Automobile Exports in Australian Market

S. No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	Australia Average Share in Indian Exports (%)		Average Tariff Barrier	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	850220	1.96	2.46	25.03	0.01	0.04	5.00	5.00
2	870600	0.29	0.34	15.37	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.00
3	731100	1.15	1.30	13.43	0.02	0.01	5.00	5.00
4	851140	0.35	0.40	13.40	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
5	842123	0.67	0.76	13.28	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
6	392690	6.34	7.15	12.84	0.01	0.01	5.00	5.00
7	840820	0.03	0.04	12.83	0.00	0.00	3.33	3.33
8	700721	0.01	0.01	12.74	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
9	851190	0.13	0.15	12.64	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
10	851150	0.19	0.21	12.41	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
11	830210	0.77	0.86	12.33	0.02	0.01	5.00	5.00
12	871690	4.26	4.78	12.18	0.07	0.04	5.00	5.00
13	830230	0.25	0.28	12.12	0.01	0.01	5.00	5.00
14	848340	6.22	6.95	11.78	0.03	0.01	5.00	5.00
15	851220	0.30	0.34	11.63	0.01	0.00	5.00	5.00
16	851110	0.02	0.03	11.42	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
17	870810	0.10	0.11	11.39	0.01	0.01	5.00	5.00
18	842131	0.32	0.36	11.33	0.01	0.02	5.00	5.00
19	851230	0.13	0.15	11.20	0.01	0.00	5.00	5.00
20	400941	1.56	1.73	10.91	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
21	851130	0.07	0.08	10.84	0.01	0.00	5.00	5.00
22	851180	0.07	0.08	10.72	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
23	870821	0.02	0.02	10.65	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
24	401120	2.94	3.24	10.30	0.00	0.01	5.00	5.00

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25	851290	0.12	0.13	10.22	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
26	940560	0.01	0.01	10.21	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
Medium Export Growth								
27	853929	0.01	0.01	9.73	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
28	870893	0.21	0.23	9.68	0.00	0.00	3.75	3.75
29	870829	1.98	2.17	9.56	0.01	0.00	3.33	3.33
30	853931	0.02	0.02	9.53	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
31	831000	0.34	0.37	9.02	0.08	0.04	5.00	5.00
32	870840	1.16	1.26	8.91	0.00	0.00	3.57	3.57
33	830120	0.05	0.05	8.83	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
34	870830	1.57	1.71	8.83	0.01	0.00	3.57	3.57
35	401220	0.00	0.00	8.77	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
36	853922	0.05	0.05	8.73	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
37	840733	0.04	0.04	8.72	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
38	840991	0.51	0.55	8.36	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
39	848360	0.95	1.03	8.32	0.03	0.02	5.00	5.00
40	870894	0.65	0.70	8.29	0.00	0.00	3.33	3.33
41	870870	1.23	1.33	8.26	0.01	0.02	3.33	3.33
42	870850	2.58	2.79	8.11	0.00	0.00	3.50	3.50
43	870899	6.45	6.96	7.90	0.01	0.00	3.75	3.75
44	870891	0.29	0.32	7.90	0.03	0.01	3.57	3.57
45	401110	0.88	0.94	7.70	0.02	0.01	5.00	5.00
46	853110	0.06	0.07	7.02	0.00	0.00	3.33	3.33
47	870892	0.16	0.17	6.62	0.00	0.00	3.33	3.33
48	853910	0.00	0.00	6.57	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
49	870880	2.43	2.59	6.37	0.02	0.01	3.33	3.33
50	840734	0.30	0.32	6.32	0.00	0.00	3.33	3.33
51	848180	19.24	20.45	6.31	0.02	0.01	2.50	2.50
52	848190	7.88	8.35	5.90	0.01	0.01	2.50	2.50
53	840999	10.20	10.80	5.87	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50

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54	871410	0.87	0.92	5.50	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
Low Export Growth								
55	842129	2.78	2.91	4.64	0.01	0.00	5.00	4.50
56	840732	0.14	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
57	840890	1.24	1.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
58	850520	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
59	853120	0.15	0.15	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00
60	853180	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
61	853190	0.21	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.01	2.50	2.00
62	853921	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00
63	870990	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 10: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select Australian Automobile Exports in Indian Market

Sl. No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	Australia Average Share in Indian Imports (%)		Average Tariff Barrier	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	870600	0.11	1.22	1033.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.00
2	700721	0.02	0.04	154.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00
3	870840	0.42	0.94	121.74	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
4	870830	0.00	0.01	112.39	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
5	840790	0.06	0.12	108.43	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
6	840991	0.05	0.10	103.28	0.00	0.00	7.50	9.00
7	851150	0.01	0.01	75.55	0.00	0.00	7.50	9.00
8	853190	0.47	0.81	71.63	0.01	0.00	10.00	10.00
9	870829	0.02	0.03	70.23	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
10	870870	0.00	0.00	69.98	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
11	842123	0.01	0.02	67.15	0.00	0.00	7.50	8.00
12	870893	0.01	0.02	59.78	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.67
13	830210	0.01	0.02	59.75	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
14	870894	0.11	0.17	58.44	0.00	0.00	7.50	9.00
15	851140	0.02	0.04	54.82	0.00	0.00	7.50	9.38
16	830230	0.00	0.00	48.61	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
17	392690	0.83	1.20	44.15	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.13
18	853180	0.31	0.43	39.92	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
19	870810	0.02	0.02	32.49	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
20	851220	0.05	0.06	31.29	0.00	0.00	9.17	10.34
21	851180	0.00	0.00	31.10	0.00	0.00	7.50	9.00
22	870850	0.01	0.01	30.86	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
23	851110	0.00	0.00	30.21	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.00
24	871410	0.02	0.02	30.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.00

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25	731100	0.03	0.04	29.34	0.00	0.01	10.00	10.00
26	840999	0.14	0.18	27.58	0.00	0.00	7.50	8.55
27	840890	0.25	0.31	26.61	0.01	0.00	7.50	9.00
28	870891	0.04	0.04	25.93	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
29	853929	0.00	0.00	25.92	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.25
30	401120	0.00	0.00	25.35	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.83
31	870880	0.05	0.06	24.73	0.00	0.00	7.50	9.00
32	870892	0.18	0.22	24.38	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.00
33	830120	0.00	0.00	24.03	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.25
34	401110	0.01	0.01	22.91	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.50
35	853990	0.01	0.01	22.16	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
36	853110	0.29	0.36	22.06	0.00	0.01	10.00	10.00
37	853939	0.00	0.00	21.57	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
38	853921	0.03	0.04	21.20	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.33
39	853931	0.05	0.06	21.15	0.00	0.01	10.00	10.00
40	851230	0.00	0.00	20.99	0.00	0.00	8.75	10.00
41	848180	2.57	3.10	20.55	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
42	831000	0.00	0.00	20.53	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
43	870899	1.60	1.93	20.36	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
44	870895	0.00	0.00	20.32	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.50
45	851290	0.04	0.04	20.30	0.00	0.00	7.50	8.00
46	400941	0.13	0.15	17.27	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
47	848340	0.64	0.75	17.20	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
48	848190	0.12	0.14	17.07	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
49	842131	0.00	0.00	15.71	0.00	0.00	7.50	8.00
50	842129	0.53	0.59	12.32	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
51	848360	0.34	0.37	11.09	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
Low Export Growth								
52	853120	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

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53	848190	258.65	258.65	0.00	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.00
54	848340	75.98	75.98	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00
55	848360	5.38	5.38	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.00
56	850220	50.23	50.23	0.00	0.05	0.08	0.00	0.00
57	850520	1.68	1.68	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
58	851110	0.56	0.56	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
59	851120	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	851130	0.79	0.79	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
61	851140	4.16	4.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
62	851150	2.73	2.73	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
63	851180	3.22	3.22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
64	851190	4.81	4.81	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00
65	851220	3.60	3.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
66	851290	5.92	5.92	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
67	853120	0.60	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
68	853180	1.39	1.39	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
69	853190	13.31	13.31	0.00	0.07	0.13	0.00	0.00
70	853939	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.75	2.20
71	870990	0.73	0.73	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00
72	871410	7.42	7.42	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 12: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select Canadian Automobile Exports in Indian Market

S.No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	Canada Average Share in Indian Imports (%)		Average Tariff Barriers	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	840820	0.34	1.53	353.47	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
2	850220	0.08	0.22	185.77	0.00	0.00	8.75	9.25
3	851240	0.01	0.03	176.43	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
4	700721	0.04	0.11	154.68	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
5	870840	0.02	0.05	120.90	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
6	870830	0.15	0.33	112.50	0.02	0.01	10.00	12.00
7	840991	0.04	0.07	103.44	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
8	851150	0.01	0.01	75.74	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
9	853190	7.11	12.19	71.49	0.01	0.02	10.00	10.00
10	870829	7.59	12.92	70.21	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
11	870870	0.32	0.54	70.19	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
12	842123	0.22	0.37	67.14	0.00	0.00	7.50	8.00
13	401140	0.00	0.00	65.99	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
14	830210	1.02	1.62	59.72	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
15	870894	9.13	14.46	58.30	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
16	851140	1.50	2.32	54.76	0.00	0.01	7.50	10.50
17	830230	0.00	0.00	48.24	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
18	392690	9.33	13.45	44.13	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.25
19	853180	3.90	5.46	39.86	0.01	0.02	10.00	10.00
20	851190	0.03	0.05	38.50	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
21	871690	0.44	0.61	38.05	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
22	870810	0.00	0.00	32.72	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.50
23	851220	0.25	0.33	31.39	0.00	0.00	9.17	10.34
24	851180	0.00	0.00	31.25	0.01	0.00	7.50	10.50
25	870850	0.02	0.03	30.83	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00

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25	851140	56.91	66.46	16.79	0.01	0.05	10.00	10.00
26	700721	0.15	0.18	16.50	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
27	853921	0.29	0.34	15.65	0.00	0.00	7.50	6.90
28	392690	59.43	68.44	15.17	0.00	0.01	8.85	8.95
29	853990	9.11	10.49	15.08	0.01	0.01	10.00	10.00
30	851130	10.31	11.68	13.34	0.17	0.08	10.00	10.00
31	871690	1.11	1.24	12.21	0.01	0.00	10.00	10.00
32	853110	2.02	2.25	11.39	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
33	851110	0.20	0.22	10.44	0.01	0.01	10.00	10.00
Medium Export Growth								
34	401110	26.57	29.13	9.63	0.01	0.05	10.00	10.00
35	401120	161.03	176.51	9.61	0.01	0.02	10.00	10.00
36	731100	113.62	124.32	9.42	0.01	0.02	10.00	10.00
37	870840	366.35	394.34	7.64	0.35	0.16	20.00	10.00
38	848340	37.51	39.75	5.98	0.03	0.02	4.86	4.75
Low Export Growth								
39	853922	3.46	3.52	1.68	0.00	0.00	10.00	9.60
40	400941	3.70	3.70	0.00	0.01	0.00	5.00	5.00
41	401310	1.01	1.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	10.00	10.00
42	830120	25.41	25.41	0.00	0.02	0.11	10.00	10.00
43	830210	1.43	1.43	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
44	830230	20.06	20.06	0.00	0.01	0.07	10.00	10.00
45	831000	1.39	1.39	0.00	0.00	0.00	17.50	19.00
46	840733	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.92	9.00
47	840790	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.02	0.02	7.23	8.67
48	840890	46.76	46.76	0.00	0.06	0.18	7.25	8.86
49	840991	124.24	124.24	0.00	0.03	0.03	9.81	8.13
50	842123	12.96	12.96	0.00	0.02	0.08	9.25	8.33
51	842129	7.42	7.42	0.00	0.01	0.01	5.00	2.50
52	842131	5.06	5.06	0.00	0.02	0.01	8.95	8.33

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53	848180	135.35	135.35	0.00	0.01	0.01	5.74	0.67
54	848190	72.03	72.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.54	0.00
55	850220	0.16	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	8.20	8.00
56	850520	0.18	0.18	0.00	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.00
57	851120	0.70	0.70	0.00	0.00	0.05	10.00	10.00
58	851150	22.42	22.42	0.00	0.10	0.05	10.00	10.00
59	851180	10.70	10.70	0.00	0.01	0.15	10.00	10.00
60	851190	1.26	1.26	0.00	0.01	0.04	7.75	9.00
61	851220	47.66	47.66	0.00	0.12	0.07	10.00	10.00
62	851230	10.09	10.09	0.00	0.01	0.05	10.00	10.00
63	851240	0.20	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.01	10.00	10.00
64	851290	12.62	12.62	0.00	0.06	0.10	10.00	10.00
65	853120	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
66	853190	2.14	2.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	8.50	8.65
67	853929	0.58	0.58	0.00	0.00	0.02	10.00	9.25
68	853931	9.55	9.55	0.00	0.00	0.06	10.00	10.00
69	853939	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
70	940560	0.14	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.00	20.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

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52	850220	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.01	0.06	0.00	1.95
53	850520	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.12	0.08	6.38	1.50
54	851220	94.93	94.93	0.00	17.14	13.88	6.88	1.83
55	851230	1.50	1.50	0.00	0.90	0.71	7.44	1.95
56	853120	0.15	0.15	0.00	0.41	2.56	0.00	0.00
57	853180	1.50	1.50	0.00	0.16	0.15	8.50	2.00
58	853190	12.09	12.09	0.00	0.37	2.69	8.50	2.00
59	853921	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.94	0.02	8.50	2.20
60	853922	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.60	0.00	8.50	0.00
61	853929	3.47	3.47	0.00	1.40	1.17	9.00	2.20
62	853931	0.84	0.84	0.00	0.42	0.84	9.00	2.20
63	853939	1.03	1.03	0.00	0.58	2.10	8.50	2.20
64	870810	51.47	51.47	0.00	5.34	6.17	8.50	2.00
65	870840	407.13	407.13	0.00	1.68	3.93	7.50	2.00
66	870850	207.59	207.59	0.00	8.07	10.57	8.50	2.00
67	870891	13.80	13.80	0.00	5.79	11.28	8.50	2.20
68	870990	0.01	0.01	0.00	7.04	2.08	8.50	5.00
69	871500	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.33	0.08	8.50	2.00
70	940560	0.08	0.08	0.00	1.24	0.10	8.50	2.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

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24	870870	11.60	15.07	29.88	0.00	0.00	10.00	13.73
25	851230	2.73	3.55	29.76	0.03	0.05	15.00	15.00
26	831000	0.52	0.68	29.63	0.02	0.01	20.00	20.00
27	830230	9.68	12.37	27.79	0.00	0.01	12.50	12.50
28	853922	0.31	0.39	27.59	0.06	0.00	13.33	13.33
29	870850	38.18	48.04	25.83	0.01	0.00	12.54	11.25
30	870891	13.93	17.45	25.30	0.02	0.02	12.50	12.50
31	870840	13.77	17.00	23.43	0.01	0.00	10.00	10.00
32	871690	48.64	59.96	23.26	0.03	0.04	7.50	9.50
33	870894	19.85	24.37	22.74	0.01	0.02	14.00	12.40
34	848190	15.33	18.79	22.53	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
35	853921	2.50	3.06	22.26	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
36	870892	38.06	46.35	21.77	0.01	0.03	12.50	12.50
37	853929	1.08	1.30	20.72	0.03	0.02	9.00	9.00
38	842123	16.73	20.18	20.63	0.00	0.01	8.00	8.00
39	731100	36.35	43.04	18.38	0.08	0.04	7.50	7.50
40	851140	13.20	15.61	18.24	0.03	0.03	7.50	7.50
41	851150	7.87	9.28	17.81	0.02	0.02	7.50	7.50
42	870899	97.88	114.66	17.14	0.02	0.01	8.33	8.33
43	851130	0.65	0.75	15.70	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
44	870880	18.44	21.15	14.70	0.01	0.01	7.50	7.50
45	851110	4.14	4.58	10.64	0.09	0.01	5.00	5.00
Medium Export Growth								
46	842131	8.38	9.11	8.62	0.01	0.02	3.75	3.75
47	392690	26.56	28.77	8.32	0.01	0.01	3.00	3.00
48	840999	60.80	65.51	7.74	0.01	0.01	6.00	3.33
Low Export Growth								
49	401310	1.24	1.24	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
50	840733	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
51	840734	3.03	3.03	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00

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52	840820	98.76	98.76	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00
53	840890	128.92	128.92	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
54	842129	17.42	17.42	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
55	848340	18.49	18.49	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00
56	848360	9.97	9.97	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
57	850220	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
58	850520	1.34	1.34	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
59	851120	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00
60	851180	0.43	0.43	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00
61	851190	3.32	3.32	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00
62	851290	4.58	4.58	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.00
63	853110	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
64	853120	0.33	0.33	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
65	853180	0.53	0.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
66	853190	0.29	0.29	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
67	870990	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
68	871410	1.46	1.46	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 16: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select South African Automobile Exports in Indian Market

S. No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	Thailand Average Share in Indian Imports (%)		Average Tariff Barrier	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	870840	0.03	0.06	122.56	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
2	870830	0.16	0.33	112.51	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
3	840991	0.15	0.30	103.26	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
4	851150	0.00	0.00	75.47	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
5	870829	3.08	5.25	70.23	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
6	870870	21.93	37.26	69.89	0.01	0.04	10.00	12.00
7	870893	2.36	3.77	59.74	0.01	0.00	10.00	12.00
8	830210	0.03	0.04	59.72	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
9	851140	0.10	0.15	54.82	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
10	830230	0.03	0.05	48.56	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
11	392690	2.22	3.20	44.16	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.25
12	853180	1.73	2.42	39.96	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
13	851190	0.02	0.02	38.53	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
14	870810	0.28	0.37	32.48	0.01	0.00	10.00	11.50
15	851180	0.01	0.01	31.12	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
16	851220	0.01	0.02	31.07	0.00	0.00	9.17	10.34
17	870850	0.01	0.02	30.78	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
18	851110	0.00	0.00	30.22	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
19	731100	0.02	0.03	29.37	0.01	0.00	10.00	12.00
20	871410	0.00	0.00	29.37	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
21	840999	2.91	3.71	27.58	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
22	840890	0.61	0.78	26.63	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
23	870821	0.09	0.11	26.21	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
24	853929	0.05	0.07	25.92	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.20

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25	870891	1.17	1.48	25.86	0.00	0.02	10.00	12.00
26	401120	0.02	0.02	25.36	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
27	870880	0.02	0.02	24.79	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
28	870892	0.96	1.20	24.42	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
29	840734	831.96	1033.99	24.28	0.19	0.25	7.50	10.50
30	401110	1.51	1.85	22.89	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.50
31	853110	0.00	0.00	22.40	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
32	853939	0.02	0.03	21.52	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
33	853922	0.03	0.03	21.23	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
34	831000	0.01	0.01	20.61	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.00
35	848180	3.33	4.01	20.57	0.00	0.00	7.50	8.00
36	870899	5.80	6.98	20.38	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
37	870895	0.10	0.12	20.31	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
38	853921	0.00	0.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	10.33
39	848340	0.16	0.19	17.20	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
40	848190	0.10	0.12	17.07	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
41	842131	0.11	0.12	15.74	0.00	0.00	7.50	8.00
42	842129	0.24	0.27	12.36	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
43	848360	0.19	0.21	11.11	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 17: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select Indian Automobile Exports in Indonesia Market

S. No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	Thailand Average Share in Indian Exports (%)		Average Tariff Barriers	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	870600	55.99	87.73	56.68	6.91	5.43	0.00	5.03
2	850220	6.05	8.67	43.38	2.01	1.15	7.75	5.00
3	840790	0.00	0.00	35.14	4.16	0.12	5.50	5.71
4	392690	10.16	13.70	34.90	0.48	0.47	13.73	11.83
5	870829	135.09	177.59	31.46	0.55	1.17	10.00	7.75
6	830210	0.50	0.66	30.85	0.05	0.04	15.00	13.50
7	871500	0.03	0.04	28.19	0.00	0.75	0.00	8.67
8	401120	262.91	335.79	27.72	6.56	8.45	12.75	9.63
9	853931	20.27	25.53	25.98	0.02	3.03	6.50	7.00
10	401310	29.78	37.30	25.24	2.63	6.08	12.75	8.06
11	401110	89.44	111.39	24.55	1.99	0.26	12.75	10.25
12	401219	0.00	0.00	24.00	0.00	1.61	13.00	6.45
13	871410	212.41	258.93	21.90	13.68	8.21	0.00	7.72
14	853929	2.83	3.42	20.98	0.07	6.33	7.75	6.95
15	870899	346.07	410.60	18.65	3.26	2.53	10.00	7.00
16	731100	13.07	15.44	18.17	1.64	1.84	5.57	6.19
17	870870	14.18	16.65	17.45	0.48	1.52	10.00	6.12
18	870880	17.30	20.23	16.91	0.85	0.49	10.00	6.68
19	830120	24.95	29.03	16.37	3.53	7.96	7.75	7.50
20	851150	1.74	2.00	15.00	0.42	0.16	4.75	4.22
21	840734	0.73	0.83	14.30	0.05	0.07	10.00	5.88
22	840820	19.13	21.74	13.65	0.43	0.37	10.78	5.10
23	870830	15.36	17.33	12.82	1.06	0.13	10.00	5.25
24	830230	7.32	8.26	12.82	0.49	0.91	12.25	5.25

Occasional Paper – 01
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25	870893	17.97	20.23	12.57	7.48	5.47	10.00	5.25
26	840733	0.04	0.04	12.16	0.00	0.00	10.00	5.00
27	870840	92.24	103.41	12.11	1.07	1.80	10.00	5.13
28	870850	55.83	62.52	12.00	1.02	0.77	10.00	5.14
29	842123	23.45	26.24	11.88	0.44	0.34	4.75	4.21
30	870894	45.20	50.52	11.78	6.17	1.65	10.00	5.25
31	870895	0.28	0.31	11.41	0.26	0.91	10.00	5.25
32	870891	4.33	4.82	11.32	1.42	0.28	10.00	5.25
33	851240	1.99	2.21	11.27	0.01	0.13	4.50	4.13
34	870810	9.09	10.10	11.14	0.23	0.40	10.00	5.25
35	851140	4.51	5.00	10.82	0.62	2.75	5.57	4.38
36	853910	9.39	10.40	10.76	0.00	0.63	6.13	4.56
37	840732	1.68	1.86	10.76	92.95	0.00	10.00	5.25
38	831000	0.14	0.16	10.68	0.03	0.21	7.75	5.00
39	848340	45.03	49.83	10.66	2.41	0.92	4.72	4.58
40	853922	7.23	7.99	10.57	0.00	0.07	8.50	5.00
41	870892	6.25	6.92	10.56	1.73	1.14	10.00	5.25
42	870821	10.95	12.05	10.10	12.01	2.01	10.00	5.25
43	853921	0.29	0.32	10.08	0.15	0.07	7.75	5.00
44	848180	149.51	164.50	10.03	1.71	1.39	4.47	3.48
Medium Export Growth								
45	853990	0.05	0.05	9.60	4.75	3.97	4.50	4.13
46	850520	0.29	0.32	9.54	0.04	0.38	4.50	4.13
47	851120	3.80	4.16	9.48	2.69	1.32	4.50	4.13
48	842129	17.47	19.09	9.29	1.08	0.96	4.50	4.13
49	851220	56.62	61.69	8.94	5.29	2.34	4.50	4.13
50	848360	5.87	6.38	8.58	0.60	0.85	5.00	5.00
51	840731	0.12	0.13	8.57	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.00
52	851290	5.80	6.29	8.54	10.88	10.65	4.50	4.13
53	851110	2.32	2.49	7.09	0.30	1.01	5.00	3.50

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

54	851230	6.29	6.73	7.00	0.55	1.55	3.92	3.10
55	700721	0.06	0.06	6.23	0.04	0.02	3.19	1.03
56	851180	5.09	5.38	5.80	0.81	0.10	4.50	3.13
57	853180	3.28	3.46	5.48	2.72	1.77	2.9	1.95
Low Export Growth								
58	840890	32.36	33.78	4.39	0.38	0.27	5.17	2.14
59	851130	12.38	12.81	3.50	5.77	6.68	3.63	1.88
60	853939	0.02	0.02	2.71	0.36	1.19	4.10	1.37
61	853110	2.06	2.11	2.28	0.06	0.66	3.19	1.03
62	400941	2.02	2.02	0.00	0.96	0.46	3.63	0.00
63	840991	148.23	148.23	0.00	1.77	2.79	0.06	0.00
64	840999	99.61	99.61	0.00	1.41	1.29	0.00	0.00
65	842131	9.14	9.14	0.00	0.40	3.37	0.00	0.00
66	848190	18.14	18.14	0.00	0.27	0.61	0.00	0.00
67	851190	1.10	1.10	0.00	3.40	0.76	1.50	0.00
68	853120	0.15	0.15	0.00	0.24	0.41	0.00	0.00
69	853190	0.44	0.44	0.00	0.09	0.38	0.00	0.00
70	871690	12.64	12.64	0.00	0.23	1.66	0	0

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 18: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select Indonesia Automobile Exports in Indian Market

S. No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	Thailand Average Share in Indian Imports (%)		Average Tariff Barrier	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	851240	0.25	0.68	176.30	0.14	0.24	8.50	11.00
2	840820	0.25	0.57	128.75	0.24	0.00	6.38	5.50
3	870830	4.23	8.99	112.48	0.56	0.57	8.50	11.00
4	870829	12.51	21.29	70.19	0.14	0.76	8.50	11.00
5	842123	3.30	5.51	67.08	0.19	0.42	6.38	8.00
6	840733	2.03	3.35	65.05	0.18	0.71	0.00	9.00
7	870893	15.04	24.00	59.53	1.38	0.93	8.50	11.00
8	851140	13.42	20.71	54.40	0.71	1.79	6.38	9.00
9	830230	0.12	0.17	48.56	1.41	0.24	8.50	11.00
10	401140	4.41	5.92	34.44	0.44	0.69	8.50	6.00
11	851180	0.42	0.55	31.01	0.04	0.08	6.38	9.00
12	851130	0.43	0.55	28.83	1.82	0.61	6.38	9.00
13	840734	0.56	0.71	27.65	0.10	0.39	6.38	9.00
14	840999	44.31	56.49	27.47	0.22	0.42	6.38	8.55
15	851120	1.93	2.46	27.13	0.01	0.77	7.50	9.38
16	870821	0.44	0.55	26.17	0.10	0.22	8.50	11.00
17	870870	105.09	131.18	24.82	1.84	7.95	8.50	6.00
18	840732	0.09	0.12	23.85	0.26	15.04	7.50	10.00
19	830120	7.09	8.76	23.67	0.32	1.16	8.50	11.00
20	870894	0.21	0.25	21.01	0.09	0.10	6.00	4.00
21	871690	0.26	0.31	19.78	0.16	0.10	8.50	6.00
22	848340	2.37	2.77	17.21	0.12	0.09	6.38	7.50
23	392690	11.80	13.66	15.79	0.48	0.29	9.25	6.00
24	842131	0.78	0.90	15.69	0.25	0.14	6.38	8.00

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

25	871410	118.02	136.33	15.52	2.07	2.63	10.00	6.50
26	851190	15.79	17.94	13.57	3.42	1.73	6.38	5.50
27	853990	0.09	0.10	11.44	0.12	0.01	8.50	6.00
28	853110	1.70	1.90	11.41	0.04	0.28	8.50	6.00
29	851110	0.58	0.64	10.68	0.17	0.54	6.38	5.50
30	401120	1.37	1.51	10.59	0.05	0.29	8.50	6.00
31	401220	0.07	0.08	10.54	0.41	0.29	9.50	5.00
32	851290	6.39	7.06	10.44	0.05	0.62	6.38	5.50
Medium Export Growth								
33	401110	160.25	174.67	9.00	2.14	6.06	8.50	6.00
34	400941	2.74	2.98	8.83	3.26	1.64	8.50	6.00
35	870880	0.19	0.21	8.72	0.10	0.06	6.00	4.00
36	870892	0.01	0.01	8.61	0.27	0.40	8.50	6.00
37	848360	0.03	0.03	7.43	0.06	0.01	6.38	5.50
38	870895	0.02	0.02	7.16	0.08	0.01	8.50	6.00
39	870899	135.31	144.85	7.05	1.47	1.08	8.50	6.00
Low Export Growth								
40	401310	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.01	8.50	2.00
41	731100	3.54	3.54	0.00	0.38	0.57	8.50	2.00
42	830210	0.12	0.12	0.00	0.45	0.06	8.50	2.00
43	831000	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.09	0.03	8.50	2.20
44	840890	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.05	0.00	6.38	1.50
45	840991	133.75	133.75	0.00	1.16	2.70	5.63	1.50
46	842129	8.87	8.87	0.00	0.52	0.33	6.38	1.70
47	848180	39.13	39.13	0.00	0.23	0.25	5.63	1.50
48	848190	16.13	16.13	0.00	0.23	0.40	6.38	1.50
49	850520	0.35	0.35	0.00	0.05	0.19	6.38	1.50
50	851220	25.58	25.58	0.00	1.23	2.48	6.88	1.83
51	851230	1.37	1.37	0.00	0.66	0.41	7.44	1.95
52	853120	0.29	0.29	0.00	0.15	0.84	0.00	0.00

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

53	853180	2.93	2.93	0.00	0.87	0.77	8.50	2.00
54	853190	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.07	8.50	2.00
55	853929	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.57	0.00	9.00	2.20
56	853931	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.48	0.09	9.00	2.20
57	870810	1.08	1.08	0.00	0.07	0.13	8.50	2.00
58	870840	433.26	433.26	0.00	0.87	5.10	7.50	2.00
59	870850	22.02	22.02	0.00	1.43	0.59	8.50	2.00
60	870891	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.38	0.30	8.50	2.20
61	870990	1.36	1.36	0.00	0.14	3.66	8.50	5.00
62	940560	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.10	0.15	8.50	2.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 19: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select Indian Automobile Exports in New Zealand Market

S. No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	Thailand Average Share in Indian Exports (%)		Average Tariff Barriers	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	870821	0.02	0.02	17.45	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
2	870829	1.14	1.30	14.05	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
3	842123	1.51	1.71	13.06	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
4	731100	0.05	0.06	12.69	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
5	851150	0.55	0.61	12.51	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
6	853910	0.00	0.01	12.32	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
7	830210	1.19	1.34	12.28	0.01	0.00	5.00	5.00
8	871690	1.89	2.12	12.12	0.00	0.00	4.50	5.00
9	853929	0.06	0.06	12.06	0.00	0.02	5.00	5.00
10	853921	0.07	0.07	11.86	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
11	853110	0.08	0.09	11.77	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
12	853931	0.00	0.00	11.76	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
13	842131	0.44	0.49	11.67	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
14	401110	2.31	2.58	11.60	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
15	870810	0.21	0.23	11.59	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
16	851220	0.75	0.84	11.58	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
17	848340	17.24	19.23	11.54	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
18	851110	0.03	0.03	11.50	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
19	400941	0.22	0.24	11.21	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
Medium Export Growth								
20	853922	1.42	1.56	9.97	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
21	700721	0.22	0.25	9.84	0.00	0.00	4.00	4.00
22	870870	1.30	1.42	9.79	0.00	0.00	4.00	4.00
23	851130	0.15	0.17	9.60	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

24	840733	0.03	0.03	8.83	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
25	870894	1.55	1.67	8.27	0.00	0.00	3.33	3.33
26	840991	1.04	1.12	8.02	0.00	0.00	2.00	2.00
27	870895	0.01	0.01	7.89	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.00
28	848360	0.51	0.54	7.56	0.00	0.00	5.00	5.00
29	870892	0.16	0.18	7.26	0.00	0.00	4.17	4.17
30	870830	2.26	2.42	6.77	0.00	0.00	3.00	3.00
31	851140	0.79	0.84	6.69	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
32	870899	7.48	7.97	6.50	0.00	0.00	4.09	4.09
33	870893	0.51	0.54	6.38	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
34	848180	3.60	3.82	6.33	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
35	830230	0.16	0.17	6.27	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
36	940560	0.01	0.01	6.24	0.00	0.00	3.75	3.75
37	848190	3.79	4.02	6.00	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
38	842129	0.84	0.89	5.83	0.00	0.00	5.00	4.97
39	853990	0.30	0.32	5.53	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
40	870850	0.67	0.70	5.40	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
41	401120	0.60	0.64	5.29	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
42	840734	0.12	0.13	5.18	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
43	870891	0.77	0.81	5.00	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
Low Export Growth								
44	392690	18.29	19.19	4.93	0.00	0.00	1.92	1.92
45	831000	0.05	0.06	4.90	0.01	0.00	2.50	2.50
46	870880	1.12	1.17	4.84	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
47	840999	1.96	2.06	4.81	0.00	0.00	2.00	2.00
48	853180	0.03	0.03	4.21	0.00	0.00	5.00	4.58
49	851230	0.18	0.18	2.96	0.00	0.00	1.25	1.25
50	401140	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
51	401310	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
52	830120	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Occasional Paper – 01
Driving in the Fast Lane without Safety Belt?

53	840820	0.13	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
54	850220	1.86	1.86	0.00	0.00	0.01	5.00	5.00
55	850520	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
56	851120	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
57	851180	0.19	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
58	851190	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
59	851240	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	851290	0.15	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
61	853120	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
62	853190	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.00	4.17
63	870840	0.73	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
64	870990	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.50	2.50
65	871410	0.82	0.82	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 20: Effect of Reduction in Tariff for Select New Zealand Automobile Exports in Indian Market

S. No.	Product Code	Exports Before (million USD)	Exports After (million USD)	Export Growth (%)	Thailand Average Share in Indian Imports (%)		Average Tariff Barrier	
					2010-14	2015-19	2010-14	2015-19
High Export Growth								
1	870829	0.02	0.03	69.76	0.00	0.00	10.00	12.00
2	842123	0.12	0.20	67.14	0.05	0.00	7.50	8.00
3	392690	0.25	0.36	44.18	0.02	0.02	10.00	10.25
4	853180	0.23	0.33	39.98	0.42	0.01	10.00	10.00
5	851190	0.00	0.01	38.64	0.01	0.00	7.50	10.50
6	851220	0.16	0.22	31.40	0.01	0.02	9.17	10.34
7	851110	0.00	0.00	31.00	0.00	0.00	7.50	10.50
8	731100	0.15	0.19	29.34	0.01	0.06	10.00	12.00
9	840999	0.02	0.02	27.64	0.02	0.02	7.50	10.50
10	853990	0.00	0.00	23.08	0.01	0.01	10.00	10.00
11	853110	0.05	0.06	22.10	0.01	0.01	10.00	10.00
12	851290	0.00	0.00	20.69	0.02	0.01	7.50	8.00
13	848180	14.43	17.40	20.55	0.10	0.12	7.50	8.00
14	870899	0.02	0.02	19.01	0.01	0.00	10.00	12.00
15	848340	0.89	1.04	17.21	0.12	0.00	7.50	7.50
16	848190	0.07	0.08	17.06	0.03	0.01	7.50	7.50
17	842129	0.19	0.21	12.34	0.01	0.01	7.50	7.50
Low Export Growth								
18	853120	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0	0

Source: Simulation results and Computations by the authors

Table 21: India’s Production Integration in GVCs - Contribution of Value Added by Source in Exports for Automobile Products (%)

Source of Value Addition	Average Share in Gross Exports (%)				
	1995-00	2001-05	2006-10	2011-14	2015-18
India	82.44	77.19	68.72	69.93	75.99
Brazil	0.09	0.25	0.22	0.43	0.29
China	0.35	0.82	2.61	2.89	4.12
EU 28	3.85	3.56	4.14	3.32	3.82
Japan	1.89	2.06	2.67	1.14	1.28
South Korea	0.52	1.12	0.92	0.91	1.19
Taiwan	0.24	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.26
United Kingdom	0.77	0.62	0.53	0.43	0.46
United States	1.30	1.34	1.61	1.81	2.34
Association of South East Asian Nations	1.12	2.35	1.97	2.09	2.32
Europe	4.67	4.54	5.41	4.48	4.63
East and South-eastern Asia	4.29	6.75	8.59	7.49	9.32
North America	1.55	2.14	2.08	2.33	2.78
South and Central America	0.30	0.51	0.59	1.12	0.82

Source: Computed by authors from TIVA (undated)